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Morphometric and acoustic variation across Mantellidae species (Anura) in
the Maromizaha rainforest (Madagascar)

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1 Introduction

Amphibians are the first clade of vertebrates to have completed the transition from aquatic to terrestrial environments, representing a key group in the evolutionary history of terrestrial vertebrates. Extant amphibians belong to the monophyletic class Lissamphibia and are divided into three orders: Anura, Urodela and Gymnophiona. Anurans (frogs and toads) are the most diversified group, counting 7955 species (according to the database of the American Museum of Natural History), able to colonise every continent except for Antarctica, and represent an excellent model group to discover evolutionary processes occurred within vertebrates due to their enormous variety of reproductive, ecological and behavioural strategies. Paleontological and molecular evidence position the origin of Anurans in the Mesozoic (Triassic) and in more than 200 million years of evolutionary history, this group developed extremely specialised morphological characteristics, such as jump locomotion, tail loss in adults and a sophisticated hearing system, contributing to the evolutionary success of this group (Reilly & Jorgensen, 2011; Sigurdson & Green, 2011). Acoustic communication represents a distinctive specialisation within this group, fundamental in reproductive and territorial contests, with species-specific acoustic signals reflecting patterns of reproductive isolation and subjected to both morphological and environmental constraints (Gerhardt, 1994). For these reasons, the study of the morphological, behavioural and physiological traits of anurans not only provides a strong model for investigating species divergence and differentiation processes, but also represents the first step toward halting their current extinction crisis and improving their biodiversity management.

Amphibians are indeed the most threatened group within vertebrates worldwide, with an impressive and worrying 41% of threatened species according to the Second Global Amphibian Assessment (SOTWA, 2023). The herpetofauna of Madagascar is still poorly known; the only group of Amphibia present on the island is Anura, and since 2006, more than 160 new species of endemic Malagasy frogs have been described (Vieites et al., 2009). According to the SOTWA, in 2023, 49% of endemic Malagasy species were threatened, ranking Madagascar 6th for the percentage of threatened amphibian species worldwide, despite being 12th for total amphibian diversity. Main threats driving amphibian declines include habitat loss, climate change, pathogen spread, invasive species, and overexploitation. Deforestation, agricultural expansion, and infrastructure development are threatening Madagascar's forests, and habitat loss and fragmentation, combined with climate change and natural or human-caused fires, represent the main threats to Malagasy

anurans (Morelli et al., 2020). Forests covering Madagascar nowadays are estimated to represent 10% of the original forest area (Andreone et al., 2008), and large fragmentation is causing diversity loss within fragments and other edge effects, such as microclimate and edge sensitivity (Schneider-Maunoury et al., 2016). Warming trends in Madagascar could also drive species upslope on mountains, threatening endangered montane endemic species (Raxworthy et al., 2008). The pet trade and subsequent overcollection of specimens are also pressuring some frog populations, especially the most colourful species, such as those of the genus *Mantella*, and flagship species, like the tomato frog (*Discophus antongilii*). Estimates suggest that about 230.000 individuals of the genus *Mantella* have been collected and exported from Madagascar between 1994 and 2003 (Andreone et al., 2011). Some larger anurans, such as *Mantidactylus grandidieri* and *Boophis goudotii*, are exploited as food in some areas of Madagascar, leading to declines in their populations. In this worrying context, the Asian common toad (*Duttaphrynus melanostictus*), probably accidentally introduced via shipping containers at the port city of Toamasina around 2010-2011, since its introduction has spread across an area of more than 850 km², with estimated populations between 7 and 21 million individuals in the eastern area of the country (Licata et al., 2023). This toad's toxicity appears to pose a severe threat to native predators (snakes, lemurs and birds), but little is known about its potential impact on endemic frogs (Marshall et al., 2018). This allochthonous species is also feared to act as a vector for *Batrachochytrium dendrobatidis*, a fungal pathogen spreading worldwide and causing dramatic increases in mortality rates in frog populations.

To contrast these threats and improve current and further conservation projects, it is fundamental to study in depth which evolutionary pressures have led to the impressive diversification that has occurred within Malagasy frogs, deepen and describe the still poorly known reproductive, ecological and behavioural traits of these species and help preserve their populations with conservation strategies, such as captive breeding projects.

Thanks to new technologies, analysis programmes and sophisticated field tools such as better performing recorders and microphones, recent studies have focused on sound analysis (Sugai et al., 2020), providing new interpretations on which selective pressures drove to the heterogeneous vocal repertoires of extant species and allowing new species recognition and description using acoustic signals as specific diagnostic characters (Köhler et al., 2017). Increasing the knowledge on the acoustic communication of anurans is fundamental to improve management projects, implement new technological tools for species detection and assess the size of populations of endangered species with new

techniques, such as passive acoustic monitoring (PAM), a non-invasive approach allowing continuous data collections of environmental sounds (Sugai et al., 2020).

With this thesis, I aimed to provide an overview of some representative species of the family Mantellidae, describing which evolutionary patterns and environmental pressures have shaped their morphological traits, using classic morphometric techniques and a geometric approach to describe head and limbs shape variation, and investigating how a complex environment such as the eastern rainforests of Madagascar and reproductive differentiation in cryptic sister species led to extremely heterogeneous acoustic signals.

1.1 Morphometry introduction

Since the birth of the natural sciences, the description of morphological forms has been used to classify organisms, using anatomical similarities to place them into taxonomic groups. This descriptive approach has then developed to a quantitative science, and the same pattern characterised morphological studies, resulting in a “quantification revolution” (Rohlf & Marcus, 1993). Classic morphometrics, a widely used approach in zoology, anatomy, botany, taxonomy and palaeontology, is the quantitative measurement of biological forms based on linear distances, angles, areas, volumes and ratios obtained from organisms or anatomical structures, analysed using univariate or multivariate statistics (Adams et al., 2004). This classic approach is based on measured distances that, to be meaningful variables, must be taken between homologous endpoints, restricted to straight-line distances. Allometry, defined as the description of scale relationships between body measures, allows the distinction between size-based and non-size-based variation and represents a fundamental concept in classic morphometrics (Jolicoeur, 1963). The use of multivariate approaches, such as principal components analysis (PCA), represented a significant development of classic morphometrics (Jolicoeur, 1963). A key limitation of classic morphometry is that size and shape are often confounded; these methodological constraints have favoured what was called “a revolution in morphometrics”: the development of geometric morphometrics, an approach that provides a more complete representation of shape (Rohlf & Marcus, 1993). Classic morphometric results, by the way, not only provide a more direct biological interpretation of the measured differences in anatomical features but can also serve as a strong comparison to the geometric approach, highlighting how these two techniques operate and the different results they yield from the same dataset. The high correlation between size and linear distance measurements in

classic morphometrics (Humphries et al., 1981) prompted the scientific community to seek new methods to extract size-free shape variables. In the last two decades of the 20th century, analyses began investigating the geometry of morphological features, giving rise to geometric morphometrics, a quantitative approach to the analysis of biological shape that preserves the geometric relationships among anatomical features (Rohlf & Marcus, 1993). Unlike traditional morphometric methods based on linear measurements, geometric morphometrics represent forms using the Cartesian coordinates of homologous landmarks, quantifying shape variation independently of size, position and orientation. This separation of shape and non-shape traits allows form comparison across individuals, making this method particularly suited for studying shape variation.

Within Mantellidae, an extreme morphological variation occurs. Size can be extremely different, even at the genus level: males of *Boophis albilabris* can weigh 50 grams (snout-vent length up to 73 mm), whereas those of *B. tasymena* rarely reach 2 grams (SVL 21-23 mm); genus *Mantidactylus* also includes both *M. grandidieri* (SVL up to 108 mm) and *M. albofrenatus* (SVL 19-23 mm). Some derived traits can be used as diagnostic characters: for example, except for the subgenus *Mantidactylus*, all subgenera of the *Mantidactylus* genus have larger tympana in males. Sexual dimorphism is present in many species of Mantellidae, sometimes with significant differences in body size (e.g., *Boophis* spp.).

Other distinct morphological traits include femoral glands, specialised in some genera and male-specific (not in the genus *Mantidactylus*, whose females have these glands too) skin glands located on the underside of hindlimbs, probably used for chemical communication (Vences et al., 2007). In the subfamily Mantellinae, their structure and appearance are more consistent, in contrast to the subfamily Boophinae, where granular glands are smaller and irregular in size, supporting the hypothesis that this trait evolved through size increase and a possible functional specialisation. Different gland arrangements arose in Mantellinae phylogeny: for example, a rosette-like, smaller and potentially derived arrangement can be observed in species of the genus *Guibemantis*, resulting from a size reduction and an increase in the number of glands, whereas some taxa of the genus *Gephyromantis* show the opposite trend (larger size, fewer glands) (Vences et al., 2007). In the genus *Mantidactylus*, semi-aquatic frogs have the most specialised femoral gland morphology, with secretory ducts converging toward a central depression; this specialisation may support the hypothesis of the functionality of femoral glands to produce pheromones or other substances during mating, and this semi-aquatic group may have adapted this trait to a

more precise application of these substances in aquatic conditions. In some species, this character allows easy recognition of an individual's sex, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 - Detail of femoral glands in a male (top) and a female (bottom) of *Spinomantis aglavei*

1.2 Bioacoustics introduction

Bioacoustics is the branch of ethology that studies sound production, transmission and reception in animals and how animals acoustically communicate, aiming to describe the relationship between the produced sounds and the nature of the environment in which they are emitted, as well as the functions that produced sounds provide (McLoughlin et al., 2019). Recent years' technological development allowed an improvement in sound sampling, analysis, storing and access (Erbe & Thomas, 2022) and taxonomy and systematic research took advantage of the collection of animal sound recordings, allowing the detection of species-specific bioacoustical signals which can be used for species recognition, as well as conservation projects (Köhler et al., 2017). New digital sound analysis techniques can easily process large numbers of recordings and detect extremely precise spectral and temporal parameters, enabling more accurate quantification of sound descriptors. Acoustic signals are the use of specialised, species-specific morphological features or behaviours to immediately or subsequently influence another individual's behaviour (Owren et al., 2010). Vocalisations, the type of sound production exhibited by most anurans, are sounds produced by the respiratory system of vertebrates, typically using the vocal cords (Köhler et al., 2017). Some frogs also produce sounds by tremulation

display, like *Agalychnis callidryas* (Caldwell et al., 2010), by tapping the gular region on the ground, like *Leptodactylus albilabris* (Lewis & Narins, 1985), or by drumming the forelimbs on the substrate, like *Leptodactylus Syphax* (Cardoso & Heyer, 1995).

Frogs mainly exhibit two types of vocalisations: advertisement calls and release calls. Advertisement calls are long-range signals produced by males primarily to attract females and to facilitate species recognition during the breeding season, whereas release calls are short-range signals produced by males in response to an erroneous male-male mating attempt (Castellano et al., 2002; Mângia et al., 2019). Other calls emitted by frogs can be classified as aggressive calls, produced by males during aggressive interactions between conspecifics defending their calling sites (Kelley, 2004), or as defence calls, in response to potential predators (Toledo et al., 2011).

Frogs' advertisement signals have been studied through the years to describe their reproductive behaviour. In most of the anuran species, only males emit advertisement calls, but in some exceptions these acoustic signals can also be performed by females (e.g., *Alytes muletensis*) (Bush & Bell, 1997) or females can reply to males' vocalisations (*Ranidae spp.*, *Rana virgatipes*, *Xenopus spp.*) (Emerson & Boyd, 1999). Advertisement calls are a distinct characteristic of anurans, produced by the alteration of respiratory behaviour, coupled with particular and highly specialised morphological characteristics. Frogs use the larynx as phonatory organ and air from the lungs is pressured through the vocal cords, whose vibration produces species-specific sounds (Zelick & Mann., 2011). Among anurans, highly diverse vocalisations have developed, shaped by phylogenetic, physical and ecological constraints. Environmental factors, ecological niche and habitat have influenced a huge differentiation in vocalisation's temporal and spectral parameters (Goutte et al., 2016). In cases of recent speciation, morphological similarity characterising sister species led to acoustic divergence, making it necessary for the females to distinguish between signals emitted by morphologically similar males of different species (Wang et al., 2017).

A morphological specialisation evolved in anurans to improve their acoustic performance is the vocal sac. Frogs vocals sacs can be single, median and subgular, bilobate subgular, paired subgular or paired lateral; in every case, vocal sacs were originally considered as resonance chambers for produced sounds but more recent functional interpretations include a facilitation in sound transmission reducing "impedance mismatch", a visual cue provided by pulsatile inflation and conservation of strain energy, helping to recycle exhaled air back into lungs without using the buccal pump, gaining speed and reducing energetical

expenses, allowing to call more frequently and for longer periods of time (Elias-Costa & Faivovich, 2025). This specialised morphological feature comprises three main elements: the gular skin, the superficial submandibular muscles (intermandibularis and interhyoideus), and the internal mucosa. In the anuran typical condition, the elastic fibres of the unfolded interhyoideus muscle cover the vocal sac mucosa (Elias-Costa & Faivovich, 2025).

Another fundamental aspect of frogs' reproductive behaviour is the amplexus. Most frogs perform external fertilisation; the female depones the eggs, which the male subsequently fertilises. To primarily have access to fertilisation, frogs have developed different types of amplexus: some of them are more common among anurans (e.g., inguinal, axillary), while others are performed only by some genera (e.g., cephalic, head straddle, independent, glued, dorsal straddle) (Carvajal-Castro et al., 2020). Within mantellids, head straddle is the type of amplexus of *Guibemantis* spp., whereas *Boophis* spp. perform axillary amplexus. Other genera studied in this thesis have largely unknown reproductive modalities (*Gephyromantis*, *Spinomantis*, *Mantidactylus*), and whether amplexus occurs remains unknown.

In this thesis, we aimed to provide an overview of the highly diverse vocal repertoires of some species of Mantellidae, with a focus on the temporal and amplitude description of the lower recognisable vocalisation subunit, the note, and of hierarchical superior levels of organisation, calls and bouts of calling. We also analysed the spectral appearance of each species vocalisations and integrated sound analyses with temperature and ecological information about the height of call sites.

1.3 Species overview

Based on molecular studies, Malagasy frogs can be subdivided into four major families, Ptychadenidae, Hyperoliidae, Microhylidae and Mantellidae.

All sampled species of this study are part of the family Mantellidae; despite the presence in the study area and several visual and acoustical detections of other extra-Mantellidae species (*Anodontohyla boulengeri*, *Heterixalus betsileo*, *Platypelis barbouri*, *Platypelis grandis*, *Plethodontohyla mihanika*, *Plethodontohyla notosticta*, *Rhombophryne alluaudi*), we chose to limit the data collection and further analyses to species included in this family.

Currently represented by 296 species and 12 genera, the number of species in the monophyletic family Mantellidae is expected to increase in the following decades, since many clearly distinct species have been described in recent years and at least 200 more are expected to be described (Vieites et al., 2009). This family, endemic to Madagascar and the Comoro Island of Mayotte, represents the largest lineage of Malagasy frogs in terms of species richness, morphological diversity, ecology and reproductive modes. Within this clade, most species are terrestrial or arboreal, but some species have evolved to live in aquatic or semiaquatic conditions. Mantellids include three major lineages corresponding to the subfamilies Boophinae, Laliostominae and Mantellinae.

Our sample includes just species of the subfamilies Boophinae and Mantellinae. Subfamilies and species descriptions reported below are largely based on the third edition of “*A field guide to the Amphibians and Reptiles of Madagascar*” by Frank Glaw and Miguel Vences (2007). For each species, the IUCN conservation status is reported (LC = least concern, VU = vulnerable, EN = endangered).

1.3.1 Boophinae

Commonly called bright-eyed frogs, the subfamily Boophinae is represented by a single genus, *Boophis*, the most abundant in terms of species richness in the family Mantellidae, currently including 88 arboreal species with large eyes and enlarged discs on the tip of their digits, able to colonise all major types of habitats in Madagascar (Raharivololoniaina et al., 2006). All species breed in running water, often in rainforest streams, and several species in this group are probably monophyletic lineages, while others are para- or polyphyletic assemblages of morphologically similar species still awaiting more definitive taxonomic revision. Species of *Boophis* were originally considered related to Asian treefrogs in the family Rhacophoridae, which has been reclassified as the sister group of the entire family Mantellidae. Originally divided into seven species groups, *Boophis* is a monophyletic assemblage characterised by a relatively large number of closely syntopic sibling species, partly distinguishable by advertisement calls and colouration (Vallan et al., 1998). This genus has been divided into two phylogenetically supported monophyletic groups: *Sahona*, which includes species breeding in ponds, and *Boophis*, a more abundant group of species breeding along streams (Hutter et al., 2018). Within Mantellidae, this genus exhibits conserved adult external morphology, and the fingers and toes of all species end in enlarged, semicircular discs with a ventral circummarginal groove (Valero et al.,

2017). Males of this genus have nuptial pads and no distinct femoral glands. Amplexus is axillary and eggs are laid directly into the water of flowing/stagnant water, where the exotrophic tadpoles complete their development. There is usually a distinctive sexual dimorphism, with males smaller than females (*B. albilabris* is an exception, with similar size in both sexes).

Boophis eye colouration is a distinctive character that fascinates pet traders and serves several functions: many species have bright-coloured irises and studies suggest this trait may correlate with arboreal habits. The bright colouration of the iris and sclera (outer iris periphery) might indeed facilitate mate recognition and serve as an aposematic defensive strategy, especially in treefrogs (Amat et al., 2013).

In our dataset, five *Boophis* subgroups are represented with a total of 9 species: *Boophis albilabris* group (*B. albilabris*), *Boophis majori* group (*B. picturatus*), *Boophis goudotii* group (*B. boehmei*, *B. burgeri*, *B. reticulatus* and *B. madagascariensis*), *Boophis albipunctatus* group (*B. aff. sibilans*) and *Boophis rappiodes* group (*B. tasymena* and *B. erythrodactylus*).

1.3.1.1 *Boophis albilabris* group

Boophis albilabris (LC) is one of the largest treefrogs in Madagascar, with males reaching a snout-vent length (SVL) up to 73 mm and females up to 81 mm. Skin colouration is usually uniformly green, but large brown patches can occur, and extensive webbing is present on both hands and feet. The iris periphery can be light-brown or greyish and breeding males are characterised by black keratinised spiny tubercles on the throat, chest and covering the dorsum. Males of *B. albilabris* emit calls in very slow-moving water, forming aggressively competing breeding aggregations (Figure 2). Non-breeding specimens can be found on trees along streams in the rainforest at 1.5-4 m. Their advertisement calls consist of unharmonious pulsed notes emitted at regular intervals. Species of the *Boophis albilabris* group share a unique vocal sac with largely expanded dorsal regions of the m. interhyoideus, resulting in paired vocal sacs on the sides of the head (Elias-Costa & Faivovich, 2025). This rare adaptation is found elsewhere only in some Lophohylini hylids (Moura et al., 2021).

Figure 2 – Breeding aggregation of males of *Boophis albilabris*, spotted on the edge of a slow-moving stream in the Maromizaha rainforest

1.3.1.2 *Boophis majori* group

Included in the *Boophis majori* group, *Boophis picturatus* (LC) is a medium-sized treefrog (males SVL: 23-33 mm) of extremely variable colouration, presenting partial hand webbing and foot webbing. The outer iris area is turquoise and the iris periphery is turquoise-blue. Specimens can have very contrasting yellow and brown dorsal patterns (Figure 3), and males present a moderately extensible single subgular vocal sac. *B. picturatus* typically lives along small streams in the rainforest, where calling males at night often sit on vegetation 1.5-3 m above the ground, emitting a single unharmonious note or a relatively slow series of up to eight such notes. In this species, tadpoles are highly adapted to the streambed sand.

Figure 3 – Male of *Boophis picturatus*, encountered in the rainforest of Maromizaha, showing a very contrasted yellow and brown dorsal pattern

1.3.1.3 *Boophis goudotii* group

The *Boophis goudotii* group comprises small to medium-sized species living along small streams in rainforests, whose males usually emit calls from perches up to 2 m above the ground. *B. boehmei* (EN) is the smallest of the sampled species of this group (males SVL: 27-29 mm), followed by *B. burgeri* (EN; males SVL: 37-38 mm) and *B. reticulatus* (LC; males SVL: 29-35 mm), while *B. madagascariensis* (LC) is one of the largest treefrogs of the Maromizaha rainforest (males SVL: 50-65 mm). Individuals of these species present a partial hand webbing (more developed in *B. madagascariensis*) and complete foot webbing. Their colouration ranges from uniform light brown across all considered species to reddish-brown in some specimens of *B. boehmei* and *B. madagascariensis*. Individuals exhibit distinct spines on the elbows and heels. Dorsally *B. burgeri* and *B. reticulatus* present a network of fine dermal reticulations, while *B. boehmei* and *B. madagascariensis*' dorsal skin is smooth.

Iris, outer iris area and iris periphery colourations represent an important diagnostic character for these species, similarly to other *Boophis* groups: *B. boehmei* has a deep red outer iris area and an orange inner iris area (Figure 4), whereas the light blue iris periphery distinguish this species from *B. rufioculis*, which has a yellowish iris periphery; in *B. burgeri* iris is yellowish-brown and the iris periphery is blue, differentiating this frog by its syntopic sister species *B. reticulatus*, which presents a yellowish iris periphery and a

silvery and orange-brown iris; *B. madagascariensis*, lastly, has a brownish outer iris area and its iris periphery is yellowish (Figure 5). Males of these species share indistinct nuptial pads and a relatively distensible single subgular vocal sac.

B. boehmei lives along small streams in rainforests and is common in the area of Andasibe, where males call at night from perches at 1-2 m high in the vegetation, emitting two types of short unharmonious notes; the slightly longer one often precedes a series of up to eight notes of the slightly shorter note type. Males of *B. burgeri* emit calls from perches in the vegetation 1.5-2 m above the ground along streams in the rainforest and their calls are composed of two types of unharmonious notes; the longer note typically precedes a series of 2-3 shorter notes. Males of *B. reticulatus* emit calls at night from perches at 1-2 m high in the vegetation. Calls in this species consist of one or more relatively long unharmonious notes, sometimes performed in up to 17 shorter note series. *B. madagascariensis* is typically found along slow-moving and swampy stretches of streams and males call at night from hidden positions in the low vegetation, up to 1.5 m high, sometimes only a few centimetres above the ground. Calls of this species are particularly complex and consist of a mix of unharmonious notes, moans, trills and clicks emitted irregularly.

Figure 4 – Couple of *Boophis boehmei*. with the male performing an axillary amplexus on the larger female, encountered in the rainforest of Maromizaha. Colouration differs between the two sexes, with the female having a darker skin than the male.

Figure 5 – Male of *Boophis madagascariensis* encountered in the rainforest of Maromizaha. The picture allows the distinction of the heel spines, the hand webbing and the colouration of outer iris area and iris periphery.

1.3.1.4 *Boophis albipunctatus* group

Among the sampled species, this group has the most uncertain species determination. The *Boophis albipunctatus* group contains several extremely similar species, both morphologically and bioacoustically, and genetic analyses in recent years have allowed the determination and description of new species within this group. These taxa have a translucent green colouration and a single subgular, highly distensible vocal sac in males (Figure 6). Calls consist of a slow series of loud and melodious whistling notes, with a second note type arranged in a fast trill-like series.

Our species determination of the sample specimens as *Boophis aff. sibilans* (LC; males SVL: 30 mm) depends on specific morphological (slightly more extended dorsal markings), ecological (more common in the area of Andasibe than *B. sibilans*) and bioacoustical traits (partly pulsed calls). The impossibility of an unequivocal species determination for the sampled individuals, due to the lack of genetic data, drove us to consider this species as a representative of the whole *B. albipunctatus* group. This level of detail, in fact, is not necessary for the morphological and bioacoustical analyses further proposed, which aim to describe evolutionary patterns that occurred within the whole family Mantellidae, at a more general level.

Figure 6 – Male of *B. aff. sibilans* vocalising from about 2 m on the vegetation along a slow-moving stream. Encountered in the rainforest of Maromizaha.

1.3.1.5 *Boophis rappiodes* group

The *Boophis rappiodes* group is a monophyletic group containing small translucent green treefrogs, usually presenting red spots or markings on their back, ventrally transparent (inner organs can be observed through the animal's skin) and usually found along streams of moderate or slow current. *B. tasymena* (LC; males SVL: 21-23 mm) and *B. erythrodactylus* (LC; males SVL: 24-25 mm) have a smooth dorsal skin, partial hand and complete foot webbing, a turquoise outer iris area and a blue iris periphery. Both species are dorsally green, with numerous evenly spaced red dots. Tips of fingers and toes are greenish in *B. tasymena* (Figure 7), in contrast to its sister species *B. erythrodactylus*, which presents red tips of hand and foot digits; this trait, as well as the advertisement calls, represents a valid species recognition criterion. Males of both species call at night from 1-3 m above the ground in the vegetation next to streams in rainforests, emitting a short, high-pitched note consisting of 2-3 clicks in *B. tasymena* and notes consisting of 4-7 (sometimes up to 14) click pulses in *B. erythrodactylus*.

Figure 7 – Male of *Boophis tasymena* encountered in the rainforest of Maromizaha. The picture shows the tip of the finger's greenish colouration, the red dots on the skin and the outer iris area and iris periphery colour.

1.3.2 Mantellinae

Mantellinae is the most diverse subfamily of Mantellidae, including the largest frogs of Madagascar (e.g., *M. grandidieri* and *M. guttulatus*, SVL up to 120 mm) as well as the smallest species (e.g., *Wakea madinika* and *Blommersia kely*, SVL: 11-15 mm). This subfamily includes typical arboreal species (*Guibemantis* spp., *Spinomantis* spp.), morphologically similar to some *Boophis*, as well as riparian or even largely aquatic stream-dwelling frogs (*Mantidactylus*) or terrestrial and independent from free water species (*Gephyromantis*).

As far as is known, all species within Mantellinae may share a derived reproductive mode in which no real amplexus occurs and the male positions itself above the female (in arboreal species like *Guibemantis depressiceps*, this occurs vertically on leaves hanging above the water). In all species, the eggs are deposited outside of the water and several genera are characterised by the presence of femoral glands, probably related to their specialised reproduction. Contrary to *Boophinae*, fingers and toes of these species are usually slightly enlarged at their hand (except for arboreal species) and always with a ventral circummarginal groove.

Our sample includes specimens of 5 genera and a total of 15 species of Mantellinae: represented genera are *Blommersia* (*B. grandisonae*), *Guibemantis* (*G. depressiceps*, *G. tornieri* and *G. liber*) *Spinomantis* (*S. aglavei* and *S. phantasticus*), *Gephyromantis* (*G. boulengeri*, *G. cornutus*, *G. malagasius* and *G. sculpturatus*) and *Mantidactylus* (*M. betsileanus*, *M. biporus*, *M. albofrenatus*, *M. melanopleura* and *M. opiparis*).

1.3.2.1 *Blommersia*

The genus *Blommersia* contains some of the smallest species of mantellid frogs (SVL: 15-26 mm) and includes 14 species. It represents semi-arboreal species usually found jumping on the ground next to water bodies or calling from the vegetation next to the water, usually a few centimetres above the ground. *B. grandisonae* (LC; males SVL: 18-23 mm) is the only species of this genus that does not breed in ponds and swamps. All specimens have foot webbing, while hand webbing is absent. The smooth dorsal skin has usually blackish bands along the flanks, bordered below by a distinct white stripe. Males have moderately distinct femoral glands and call at night from the vegetation, up to 50 cm

above the water of slow-moving streams. Calls consist of a long-pulsed chirping note and a rapid series of 5-6 short-pulsed notes.

1.3.2.2 *Guibemantis*

Guibemantis includes 26 treefrog species of heterogeneous size (SVL 22-59 mm). Species of this genus belong to two subgroups: the subgenus *Guibemantis*, including rather large frogs with very large relative hand lengths very similar to *Boophis*, and *Pandanusicola*, smaller frogs with smaller hands and mostly specialised to live in the leaf axils of *Pandanus* plants. Species of the subgenus *Guibemantis* have an external metatarsal tubercle and foot webbing, but the absence of hand webbing. Males have a moderately distensible bright white single subgular vocal sac and relatively distinct femoral glands. Eggs are usually deposited on vegetation overhanging large ponds and swamps and after hatching, the tadpole drops into these water bodies where it completes its development. *G. depressiceps* (LC; males SVL: 32-45 mm) has a smooth dorsal skin with variable colouration, often with a laterally uniform dark brown head (Figure 8). This species is an explosive breeder, with many males emitting calls at night from vegetation 1-2 m above ponds in rainforests. Calls are composed of 1-7 rapidly repeated pulses. When mating occurs, the male positions himself over the female, rubbing her shoulder and head with the underside of his shanks. *G. tornieri* (LC; males SVL: 42-51 mm) is morphologically similar to *G. depressiceps*, except for its more extended foot webbing reaching the terminal disc of the fifth toe. Males of this species emit loud calls, composed of a single note of 2-6 relatively slow repeated pulses, from the vegetation over ponds or swamps in rainforests. Included in the *Pandanusicola* subfamily, *G. liber* is a non-*Pandanus*-breeding species that probably secondarily lost this reproductive specialisation, returning to breed in open waters, similarly to species of the subgenus *Guibemantis*. *G. liber* (LC; males SVL: 21-29 mm) has a smooth dorsal skin and extremely variable patterns, usually green and light brown (Figure 9). Males have a largely extensible white single subgular vocal sac and diffused femoral glands. Calls are emitted by males at night from vegetation 1-2 m above small pools and ditches and consist of a series of 7-10 unharmonious notes of complex structure. As for *B. sibilans*, this species recognition is challenging without genetic data. Another similar species which could have been sampled is *G. aff. albolineatus*, but the morphological and bioacoustical similarity of these two species led us to consider the sampled individuals as a unique group under the name of *G. liber*, as a representative for

the whole *Pandanusicola* subfamily, since we cannot have the certainty that every specimen in our sample is conspecific.

Figure 8 – Specimen of *Guibemantis depressiceps* over eggs, spotted on a leaf pending on a pond.

Figure 9 – Male of *Guibemantis liber* encountered in the rainforest of Maromizaha.

1.3.2.3 *Spinomantis*

This genus includes 16 species and contains both arboreal frogs living along streams in most of Madagascar's rainforests and whose vocalisations, loud abrupt calls often reminding a “metallic” sound, can be heard from long distances, and a variety of smaller and more terrestrial species. The two sampled species, *S. aglavei* (LC; males SVL: 40-50 mm) and *S. phantasticus* (LC; males SVL: 36-38 mm), have conspicuous dermal spines and fringes on their bodies and limbs, making these frogs experts in mimicry. Both these species have a dorsally granular skin with ridges and folds and *S. aglavei* is dorsally olive to metallic greenish (Figure 10), while *S. phantasticus* has a more defined green-brown dorsal patterning. These two species differ ventrally: *S. aglavei* has a uniform whitish ventral colour and males have whitish femoral glands, whereas *S. phantasticus* has a greenish ventral side and greenish femoral glands. Males of these species have a largely distensible white subgular vocal sac and emit calls from high in the canopy, typically 1.5-3 m above the ground along streams. *S. aglavei* has two note types: a very loud and intense series of up to nine short “metallic” notes and a short and pulsed croak. Males of *S. phantasticus* emit calls consisting of a series of 4-5 “metallic” double click notes.

Figure 10 – Male of *Spinomantis aglavei* encountered in the rainforest of Maromizaha.

1.3.2.4 *Gephyromantis*

Gephyromantis contains 61 frog species that have evolved to become independent from free water for reproduction. Some species of the subgenus *Duboimantis* have free-swimming and feeding tadpoles in streams, but others (e.g., the subgenus *Gephyromantis*) probably are direct developers, with small froglets hatching directly from eggs deposited in the leaf litter. Females of this genus are usually slightly larger than males, while males of the subgenus *Gephyromantis* have a slightly larger tympanum than females. The vocal sac of *Gephyromantis* spp. is usually paired subgular, but in some cases is single subgular.

G. boulengeri (Figure 11) is a predominantly dark brown small frog (LC; males SVL: 25-30 mm), presenting a granular dorsal skin without ridges. Hand webbing is absent, foot webbing is rudimentary and males have distinct femoral glands and blackish paired subgular vocal sacs. Males usually call during the day from the forest floor or from perches up to 100 cm above the ground and their call consists of a loud and fast series of 7-20 melodious notes.

Two sampled species of the subgenus *Duboimantis*, *G. cornutus* (Figure 12) and *G. sculpturatus* (Figure 13), share the presence of dorsolateral dermal ridges (weakly expressed in *G. cornutus*) and a brownish skin colour. Both also have small supraocular spines and *G. sculpturatus* (LC; males SVL: 38-43 mm) also have distinct heel spines. Males of *G. sculpturatus* have two paired subgular vocal sacs and indistinct femoral glands; at night, they emit loud series of up to 22 short melodious notes with a clear pulsed component from leaves up to 2m above the ground, not necessarily close to water bodies, and they do not aggregate in choruses. Males of *G. cornutus* (VU; males SVL: 38-40 mm) have a greyish, largely distensible, single subgular vocal sac and call from perches about 1.5 m above the ground in the vegetation, at some distance from the water. *G. cornutus* calls consist of a slow series of unharmonious notes.

Representing the subgenus *Laurentomantis*, a group of small forest frogs with secretive habits difficult to observe, *G. malagasius* (Figure 14) is a small species (LC; males SVL: 22-24 mm) with an extremely granular brown dorsum and ventrally grey with red colour of the proximal part of the limbs. Males have distinct femoral glands and call from perches 5-50 cm above the ground, emitting discrete unharmonious notes composed of 15-43 widely spaced pulses. New cryptic species of the *G. malagasius* complex have been described by Vences et al., 2022). Similarly to the *B. albipunctatus* group and

Pandanusicola group, we considered the sampled individuals as representative of the whole complex, under the name of *G. malagasius*.

Figure 11 – Male of *Gephyromantis boulengeri* on a calling site about 1.5m above the ground in the Maromizaha rainforest.

Figure 12 – Vocalising male of *Gephyromantis cornutus* on a calling site about 1.5m above the ground in the Maromizaha rainforest, with the singular subgular vocal sac extended.

Figure 13 – Male of *Gephyromantis sculpturatus* on a calling site about 1.5m above the ground in the Maromizaha rainforest.

Figure 14 – Male of *Gephyromantis malagasius* on a calling site about 50cm above the ground in the Maromizaha rainforest.

1.3.2.5 *Mantidactylus*: subgenus *Brygoomantis*

Subgenus *Brygoomantis* contains small to medium-sized semiaquatic frogs, often very common and mostly found along streams. Some species of this subgenus can also be found in swamps or at the edge of ricefields, but in all cases the water is not completely stagnant. Their calling is inconspicuous, emitted both day and night and, despite some differences,

their low intensity combined with a generally similar structure makes them hardly usable as a diagnostic character.

M. betsileanus (Figure 15; LC; males SVL: 23-28 mm) is a very common species in mid-altitude rainforests of eastern Madagascar. Dorsal colouration is very variable and dorsal skin is moderately granular, with defined dorsolateral folds. This species also typically has a distinct white tip on the snout. Males have a weakly distensible single subgular vocal sac and relatively small femoral glands. They call along slow-moving streams, but also in swampy areas, ditches and at the edge of ricefields, day and (mostly) night from positions on the ground, often from within small open cavities. Calls consist of a long and fast-pulsed note.

M. biporus (LC; males SVL: 26-27 mm) comprises a complex of poorly known species of quite distinct morphology. Their snout is relatively short and their colour is variable, often yellowish brown. Males mostly call during the day from swamps derived from the flood of small streams, emitting a slow series of 3-8 short pulsed notes.

Figure 15 – Male of *Mantidactylus betsileanus* encountered in the rainforest of Maromizaha.

1.3.2.6 *Mantidactylus*: subgenus *Chonomantis*

Chonomantis is a subgenus of *Mantidactylus* of relatively small frogs living along streams, but usually not very close to the water. Males of this group are usually smaller than females, have distinctly larger tympanum sizes, distinct femoral glands and a weakly distensible single subgular vocal sac. This subgenus is also phylogenetically closely related to the subgenus *Brygoomantis*.

M. albofrenatus (EN; males SVL: 19-23 mm) has prominent femoral glands in males and a distinct frenal stripe continuing until the nostril. Males call mostly during the day from hidden positions on the ground or from vegetation up to 50 cm above the ground in the immediate proximity of small streams, emitting a rapid series of 31-36 pulsed notes.

M. melanopleura (LC; males SVL: 30-40 mm) have smaller and indistinct femoral glands in males and shares with *M. albofrenatus* the frenal stripe reaching the nostril. Dorsally, they are light brown, often with a diamond-shaped marking. Males call mostly during the day from the ground or from elevated positions up to 50 cm above the ground, emitting a rapid series of 12-48 short pulsed notes.

M. opiparis (Figure 16; LC; males SVL: 24-26 mm) has small femoral glands in males and its frenal stripe does not reach the nostril, contrary to the other two previously described species. Dorsally, it often has a diamond-shaped marking, similarly to *M. melanopleura*. Males call mostly during the day, near streams, from up to 50 cm above the vegetation.

M. opiparis and *M. melanopleura* often form mixed choruses characterised of boosts of calling activity emitted after long silence intervals, sometimes running wave-like along the stream. Males of *M. opiparis* emit a series of 23-25 short pulsed notes, longer than in *M. melanopleura* and emitted more slowly.

Figure 16 – Male of *Mantidactylus opiparis* encountered along a slow-moving stream in the Maromizaha rainforest.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Study area

Data collection took place in the mid-altitude rainforest of Maromizaha, located approximately 140 km east of the capital, Antananarivo, on Route Nationale 2, within the Moramanga district of the Alaotra-Mangoro region (Figure 17). This forest is part of the large Ankeniheny-Zahamena Corridor (CAZ), a protected area covering 380.000 hectares, which includes the majority of the rainforest of the country and geologically unique habitats (Ravaloharimanitra et al., 2011). In addition to the already mentioned Maromizaha rainforest, CAZ includes five more national parks and reserves: Zahamena National Park, Zahamena Reserve, Andasibe-Mantadia National Park, Mangerivola Reserve and Analamazaotra Reserve (Portela et al., 2012). The nearby village of Anevoka hosts GERP (Groupe d' Étude et de Recherche sur les Primates de Madagascar), a non-governmental association established in 2008 that aims to raise awareness among local communities of the importance of the forest and its biodiversity. To accomplish these goals, several projects led by GERP took place to develop the population's wealth, create new job opportunities, help preserve the protected area, and provide alternative, less-impactful agricultural techniques. This increasing awareness is crucial to contrast *tavy*, a common and invasive practice that involves burning natural vegetation with uncontrolled fire to obtain arable land and make the soil fertile, resulting in serious damage to both fauna and vegetation (GERP, 2008). Maromizaha is a 2.150 ha rainforest ranging from 800 to over 1200 m above sea level, which in 2001 was classified as a protected area by the Madagascar government, due to the unique biodiversity hosted (Avesani Zaborra et al., 2012). The reserve of Maromizaha is characterised by tropical rainforest, a rapidly disappearing habitat in Madagascar, mainly due to deforestation (Morelli et al., 2020). Three main areas can be distinguished in this reserve: the core area, the ecotourism area, and the buffer area, which is more heavily used by humans (Figure 18). In particular, human activities, led and supported by GERP (such as agriculture and beekeeping), take place in the tampon area near the villages and the main road. Along the western margin of the reserve, an active reforestation project is underway to restore a habitat that has been largely exploited over the last few decades.

The rainforest of Maromizaha represents a unique hotspot for a heterogeneous fauna, including 13 species of lemurs, more than 80 species of birds, and an estimated 60

amphibian and 30 reptile species (Gamba et al., 2013). The conservation status of many Malagasy species is critical, and this reserve's fauna is no exception. Several lemurs are classified by the IUCN as critically endangered (CR), such as *Indri indri*, *Propithecus diadema*, *Varecia variegata editorium*, while others are classified as endangered (EN), such as *Daubentonia madagascariensis* and *Allocebus trichotis*, and numerous species are classified as vulnerable (VU). Many anurans in Madagascar are threatened and have a very limited distribution. The eastern rainforests of the country are home to several locally endemic frog species and this reserve also hosts some species listed as endangered, like *Boophis boehmei*, *Boophis burgeri* and *Mantidactylus albofrenatus*, or vulnerable, like *Gephyromantis cornutus*. An impressive diversity of plants is also present in this forest, with 88% of the species endemic to Madagascar.

Figure 17 – Map created with the software QGIS, showing the position of the three biggest cities in the central-East area of Madagascar and the location of the Alaotra-Mangoro region.

2.2 Field work and data collection

The data collection took place in the area surrounding the polyfunctional centre of Maromizaha, a research centre located about an hour's walk from the nearest village, Anevoka. Transects were not pre-defined and the active research of vocalising individuals was performed with visual encounters following the many stream edges and ponds of the rainforest, accompanied by two local guides. Most-walked areas include the area between Campsite 2 and Campsite 3, whereas the surrounding area of Campsite 1 was surveyed fewer times (Figure 18). Fieldwork has been carried out between January 19th and May 12th, 2025. This period was chosen because it partially overlaps with the rainy season, which corresponds to the peak of reproductive activity in anuran populations. Night surveys usually focused on a specific habitat, depending on weather conditions and on the species we aimed to sample, particularly those that had been less recorded. Most of the time, our active search for animals focused on stream edges and ponds; however, many forested areas (defined as areas of the forest without immediate nearby streams or ponds) were crossed along the pathways, giving us the opportunity to expand the sample with species whose habitat could be defined as forestal, according to Vences et al. (2008).

As previously mentioned, weather conditions influenced the choice of which species sample each night. Some species tend to vocalise more during rainy nights (e.g., *Boophis aff. sibilans* and *Spinomantis aglavei*), whereas others are more active under drier conditions. Rainy nights were characterised by a rich and intricate mix of calls, although heavy rain reduced recording quality. After the first month, which was fundamental for becoming familiar with species morphology, acoustic repertoires and preferred habitats, data collection expanded to include species representative of the different lineages within the family Mantellidae and, for each species, to obtain as large a sample size as possible.

Fieldwork consisted of two sessions, one at night and the other in the morning.

Night work (3.30-4 hours, typically from 20.00 h until 00.00 h) – Five nights per week, active research of vocalising males of the family Mantellidae was carried out. Once vocalising individuals were found, vocalisations were recorded using a recorder (Olympus LS-100 Multi-track Linear PCM) and a directional microphone (Sennheiser K6 ME66). The recording lasted approximately 5-20 minutes, depending on the number of recorded vocalisations and the species-specific call rate. After recording, frogs were caught using nitrile gloves to avoid skin damage. Because temperature is known to affect many acoustic properties of anurans' advertisement calls (Gerhardt & Mudry, 1980), both cloacal and substrate temperatures at the calling site were measured using a digital thermometer (Appa

51, Appa Technology Corporation, Hsientien, Taiwan). Temperature data and additional observations (e.g., interactions with other males, interactions with females, posture exhibited during the recording) were appended to each audio file to ensure proper data traceability. Frogs were subsequently placed in perforated plastic boxes, with wet napkins at the bottom and taken to the centre for further data collection the following morning.

Figure 18 - Map created with the software QGIS, showing the distinction of the three different areas of the Maromizaha protected area and the location of the mentioned campsites.

Morning work (3 hours, from 9.00 h until 12.00 h) – Frogs were anaesthetised by immersion in a 0.1% solution of MS-222 Sandoz for 3-5 minutes, then weighted at the nearest 0.1 g using a digital scale and placed on a graph paper (Figure 19) where they were photographed with an iPhone 14, mounted on a stative and supported with a ring light.

Because all morphometric parameters (see below) were measured from these images, measurement repeatability was assessed by photographing 15 randomly selected frogs from 12 species twice, repositioning them on graph paper while still anaesthetised. After recovery, frogs were released at the location where they had been captured the previous night. The digital scale and the graph paper were sanitised after handling each individual, whereas nitrile gloves were changed once for working day. This protocol was adopted as a

compromise between minimising the risk of contamination, avoiding potential damage to the fragile skin of frogs and limiting plastic waste production. All used nitrile gloves, along with other plastic waste generated during field work, were returned to Italy.

Species identification was supported by a mixed approach that combined morphological traits and comparison of the obtained recordings with the online database FonoZoo, provided by the National Museum of Natural History of Madrid. This free and accessible sound library contains 62.424 acoustic recordings of more than 15.151 species, representing a useful tool for acoustic researchers worldwide.

A small sample of females was also caught but was not included in subsequent analyses. Given the preliminary nature of this study, no target species were defined a priori; instead, the recorded sample consisted of commonly encountered Mantellidae species vocalising. This means that the representation of species in our sample does not reflect their actual abundance in the forest. For example, species such as *Mantidactylus femoralis* were not included because recordings were difficult to obtain, despite their high abundance in the Maromizaha rainforest.

Figure 19 - Sedated male of *Guibemantis depressiceps* placed on graph paper. Limbs were positioned to achieve a 90° angle between segments. The note below reports individual code, date and weight in grams.

2.3 Individual recognition

To determine whether an individual was caught more than once during data collection, various techniques were considered. Among these, the method proposed for *Mantidactylus betsileanus* (Edmonds et al., 2019), based on the comparison of ventral patterns (the arrangement of spots on the abdomen), provided a reliable and widely applicable method. This method is objective, minimally invasive compared to other methods, such as pit tags or clipping, and it can also be applied retrospectively from photographs, reducing the time required for animal manipulation. Moreover, it can also be supported by automated image-recognition tools, such as WildID.

In our study, we adopted this approach, by selecting the most informative body patterns for each species. In most species, we considered the disposition of spots on the abdomen, while in other species we identified subgular patterns (e.g., *B. boehmei*), dorsal spots (e.g., *B. tasymena*), or patterns along the mouth margin (e.g., *S. aglavei*). Individual recognition was important for constructing the final dataset used in subsequent analyses. It allowed us to extend the sample used for repeatability estimates, and it provided preliminary information about capture-recapture probabilities, important for future ecological studies in Maromizaha.

2.4 Ecological matrix

An ecological matrix was used to account for interspecific differences in habitat preference and calling sites. Specifically, we used two variables to describe these preferences: one representing the general habitat and the other the calling site of each species.

The habitat variable was derived from Vences (2008), who distinguishes three main habitat categories among the mantellids considered: forest, stream edge and arboreal. The arboreal guild includes species that are predominantly or exclusively arboreal; stream-edge frogs are terrestrial to semi-aquatic species mainly found along streams; lastly, forest frogs are species that do not reproduce in water bodies and are therefore usually found evenly spaced in the forest (Vences 2008).

The second ecological variable describes the typical height of the calling site. This was defined as ordinal variable based on both bibliographic sources and field observations, distinguishing four height categories: 0, 50, 150 and 250 cm above the ground. The first category (0 cm) includes species whose males typically emit calls from the ground, in the

leaf litter, in swampy areas or along slow-moving streams. The second category (50 cm) includes typically terrestrial species that emit calls from the vegetation, up to approximately 50 cm above the ground. The third category (150 cm) includes species calling from visible positions on the vegetation, at heights between 50 and 200 cm. The last category (250 cm) includes species whose males emit calls from the canopy, usually from calling sites that are not visible and are more than 2.5 m above the ground.

Both these variables were used into subsequent phylogenetic analyses to test for associations between ecological traits, morphology, and acoustic parameters.

2.5 Morphometry methods

2.5.1 Landmarks and semilandmarks placement

Data preparation for the analyses included placing landmarks and semilandmarks on images of the dorsal sides of each individual using the Python programme “morfometria” (<https://github.com/castellanosergio/morfometria.git>). The procedure involved several steps.

1. Images were first rotated so that the snout-vent axis (SVL) was aligned vertically, with the snout positioned upwards and the vent downwards. A 50 mm reference segment (obtained from the graph paper on which the animals were placed) was used to convert pixel measurements in millimetres.
2. Landmarks and semi-landmarks placement. A total of 33 landmarks were digitised on each specimen to capture variation in body shape; 11 landmarks were on the head, two landmarks on the spine, 14 landmarks on the forelimbs, and six on the hindlimbs (see Table 1). This set of homologous anatomical points was complemented with four groups of semi-landmarks, each formed by 16 points evenly spaced, respectively, along the left and right margins of the head and the left and right margins of the abdomen (Figure 21). However, this last set of semi-landmarks was not included in subsequent analyses due to low repeatability (see below).

3. Landmarks alignment. After landmark digitisation, additional adjustments were applied to reduce the effect that variability in specimen disposition could have had on shape description. Two types of adjustments were carried out. First, for the distal portions of the fore- and hindlimbs, the landmark at the tip of the digit was often not aligned with the base of the limb (tarsus) due to flexion at the interphalangeal joints. In these cases, a polyline was drawn along the phalanges and subsequently straightened, effectively aligning all segments along a common direction. Second, although specimens were positioned to approximate a right angle between limb segments, deviations from 90° were common. In these cases, the frog silhouette was standardised by imposing a 90° angle between limb segments (e.g., between LArmPit-LElbow and LElbow-LMCarp), obtaining a comparable figure for each individual (Figure 20), while hand digits were reoriented considering a 30° angle between each one (equal division of a 90° angle between digit I and digit IV).

Table 1 – List of landmarks and semilandmarks grouped per anatomical region

Anatomical region	Landmarks	Semilandmarks
Spine - Thorax	Vent, Cervical	L Chest (16 semilandmarks Vent-Cervical)
		R chest (16 semilandmarks Vent-Cervical)
Head	Snout, LHead1, LHead2, LHead3, Rhead1, Rhead2, Rhead3, LNostril, RNostril, LMidEye, RMidEye	LHead (16 semilandmarks LHead3-Snout)
		RHead (16 semilandmarks RHead3-Snout)
Anterior limb	LArmPit, LElb, LMCarp, LFingHand1, LFingHand2, LFingHand3, LFingHand4, RArmPit, RElb, RMCarp, RFingHand1, RFingHand2, RFingHand3, RFingHand4	
Posterior limb	LKnee, LTar, LToe, RKnee, RTar, Rtoe	

Figure 20 – Example of landmarks placement on an individual of *Spinomantis aglavei*. Details of head and hand landmarks on the top right. As previously explained, automatically detected green lines do not follow the actual digit orientation because standardised angles are imposed, reorienting the obtained distances.

Figure 21 – Example of semilandmarks placement on an individual of *Spinomantis aglavei*. Green dots follow the shape of the head and chest. Semilandmarks define a curve between and including two landmarks, in this case Snout - L/R Head 3 for the head shape and Vent – Cervical for the chest shape.

2.5.2 Repeatability

Testing for repeatability is fundamental in morphometric analyses to ensure that observed variation reflects true biological differences rather than measurement error, thereby validating the reliability of landmark placement and data acquisition procedures.

Consistency across repeated procedures is validated by high repeatability, supporting the use of the obtained data in subsequent statistical and comparative analyses. Low repeatability, by contrast, may reflect unreliable methods and produce altered results. To demonstrate the reproducibility of our method and the impact of animal placement on further results, a sample of 15 frogs was removed from the graph paper (after dorsal and ventral pictures were taken, as for other individuals), and subsequently replaced in the same positions to obtain new images. This process allowed us to assess the impact of animal placement on measurement errors and establish the validity of this method. Each

individual was measured four times: two measurements were obtained from the same image, and two pictures of the same individual, repositioned on the graph paper, were taken, yielding four distinct landmark sets per individual. The double measurement of the same picture allowed us to establish the measurement error arising from landmark placement, while the comparison between different pictures of the same individual, each placed twice on the graph paper, aimed to validate the animal placement method and assess its influence on subsequent measurements.

2.5.3 Classic approach to morphometry

In this approach, we operated on measured distances between positioned landmarks. Distance calculation was performed in Python using NumPy and Pandas. We set the vent landmarks as the origin for each figure before computing the Euclidean distances (the straight-line distance between two points in space) between selected landmarks as described in Table 2 and showed in Figure 22. All distances were log-transformed for subsequent analyses. For all symmetric distances, we calculated the arithmetic mean of left and right values.

Figure 22 – Example of defined distances on an individual of *Spinomantis aglavei*. Blue lines represent each measured straight line between two defined landmarks. On the right, a detail of the single digits' distances. As previously described, straight lines do not necessarily accurately overlie the body picture, due to imposed angle adjustments.

Table 2 – Description of each calculated distance, the proximal and distal landmarks of the measured straight line and the operational definition of each body segment.

Body segment	Proximal landmark	Distal landmark	Operational Definition
SVL	Snout	Vent	Straight-line distance between the anterior tip of the snout and the posterior margin of the cloacal opening
Humerus	ArmPit	Elbow	Straight-line distance between the most proximal point of the humerus and the lateral epicondyle
Radius/Ulna	Elbow	MCarp	Straight-line distance between the most proximal point of the radius/ulna and the most proximal point of the metacarpals
Digit IV	MCarp	Finger Hand 4	Straight-line distance between the most proximal point of the metacarpals and the distal end of the distant phalanx - digit IV
Digit III	MCarp	Finger Hand 3	Straight-line distance between the most proximal point of the metacarpals and the distal end of the distant phalanx - digit III
Digit II	MCarp	Finger Hand 2	Straight-line distance between the most proximal point of the metacarpals and the distal end of the distant phalanx - digit II
Digit I	MCarp	Finger Hand 1	Straight-line distance between the most proximal point of the metacarpals and the distal end of the distant phalanx - digit I
Femur	Vent	Knee	Straight-line distance between the posterior margin of the cloacal opening and the lateral femoral epicondyle
Tibia/Fibula	Knee	Tarsals	Straight-line distance between the lateral femoral epicondyle and the medial malleolus
Foot	Tarsals	Toe	Straight-line distance between the medial malleolus and the most distal point of the most distal phalanx

2.5.4 Geometric approach

Geometric morphometric analyses were conducted following the protocol described by Theska et al. (2020). Landmark coordinates (the same used for classic morphometric analyses) have been subjected to a Generalised Procrustes Analysis (GPA), using the R package *geomorph*. GPA scales configurations to unit centroid size, translates them to a common origin, and rotates them to minimise the sum of squared distances between corresponding landmarks, allowing shape analysis in an Euclidean space (Rohlf & Silce, 1990). As we did for the classic approach, we imposed bilateral symmetry on each individual using the *geomorph* function *bilat.symmetry*. Asymmetry, although biologically meaningful, was not a focus of this study. In addition, asymmetry strongly affected deformation grids, reducing their interpretability, and it may partly represent artefact due to minor inconsistencies in landmark positioning or imperfect specimen positioning during imaging.

To separately capture variation in head shape and limb proportions, we split landmark configuration into two subsets and applied GPA to each subset independently. One subset included all landmarks and semilandmarks describing head shape, whereas the other included the landmarks related to SVL and limb proportions. In this way, we were able to analyse shape variation separately across body regions that are likely to have been influenced by different ecological pressures and phylogenetic constraints.

Variables from both GPA subsets were subjected to PCA (Theska et al. 2020), obtaining separate principal components for head shape and limb proportions. Along each principal component, we derived two deformation grids by comparing the mean shape to the extreme shapes. Extreme configurations (e.g., minimum and maximum PC scores) were visualised using thin-plane spline interpolation (Theska et al., 2020). These grids show the type of shape variation captured by each component.

2.5.5 Phylogenetic approach

In classic morphometrics, phylogeny is essential to distinguish size-related similarity from traits influenced by evolutionary patterns. However, apparent correlations among morphometric variables or between morphology and ecological factors may reflect shared ancestral traits rather than adaptive processes (Rohlf & Marcus, 1993). The inclusion of phylogenetic information allows classic and geometric morphometric data to be interpreted

in light of evolutionary processes, determining whether observed patterns result from divergence, constraint, or convergence; phylogenetically informed analyses indeed help identify cases of convergent evolution and adaptive shape change that may be obscured when phylogeny is ignored. Aiming to incorporate phylogenetic information, the list of collected species was entered into the TimeTree database (<https://timetree.org/>) to generate a phylogenetic tree in Newick format, which is required by most software used for comparative analyses. Two species (*Spinomantis phantasticus* and *Mantidactylus albofrenatus*) were not available in the TimeTree database and were therefore manually added to the tree. For these species, branch lengths were assigned arbitrarily, while their phylogenetic placement followed current taxonomic knowledge. Specifically, *S. phantasticus* was added as the sister species of *S. aglavei*, whereas *M. albofrenatus*, belonging to the subgenus *Chonomantis*, was placed within its subgenus clade, with its branch added close to the other two sampled species of *Chonomantis* (*M. opiparis* and *M. melanopleura*). The phylogenetic tree was midpoint-rooted before performing comparative analyses.

2.5.6 Statistical Analyses

We performed a series of analyses that included both descriptive approaches, aimed at summarising patterns of morphological variation (e.g., PCA), and inferential statistical tests designed to evaluate specific evolutionary and ecological hypotheses (e.g., phylogenetic signal, phylogenetic regression, and post-hoc comparisons).

To assess whether our landmark configuration produces clear and replicable results, and can therefore be reliably used to describe head and limb shape variation in frogs, we followed the protocol proposed by Theska et al. (2020), based on the estimation of average shape repeatability. This was computed by averaging the repeatability of Procrustes coordinates for each set of landmarks (Theska et al., 2020). The x- and y-coordinates of the “vent” and “snout” landmarks were excluded from the analysis because the images were translated and rotated so that the vent coincided with the origin of axes and the snout-vent segment aligned with the y axis (see paragraph 2.5.1). Variance estimates were obtained using the *brms* package in R (Burkner, 2017; Burkner, 2018), which adopts a Bayesian inference based on STAN. Posterior distributions were used to estimate expected variances, with their 95% credible interval (CIs).

In both the classic and the morphometric geometric approaches, a Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was conducted to reduce the dimensionality of the data while capturing as much of the total variation as possible. In the classic approach, PCA was performed on the log-transformed values, whereas in the geometric morphometric approach, PCA was carried out directly on the Procrustes coordinates. In both cases, scores of the first three principal components (PC1-PC3) were retained for subsequent analyses.

We then investigated the presence of phylogenetic signal in morphometric traits by using Pagel's λ and Blomberg's K statistics. These tests were carried out both on the whole dataset of Mantellidae and, separately, on the two subfamilies Boophinae and Mantellinae. Pagel's λ rescaled the branch lengths of our phylogenetic tree to best fit the trait data under a Brownian motion (BM) model, assessing how much the phylogenetic tree explains the covariance in the trait data. Values range from 0 (no phylogenetic signal) to 1 (trait evolution consistent with a BM). The significance of λ was evaluated using likelihood ratio tests comparing the fitted model with models in which λ was fixed at 0 and 1 (Pagel, 1999).

Blomberg's K assessed the strength of phylogenetic signal relative to expectations under Brownian motion, with $K \approx 1$ corresponding to conformity to the Brownian motion model, $K < 1$ indicating a weaker phylogenetic signal, and $K > 1$ representing a stronger signal than expected under a Brownian motion model. Statistical significance of K was assessed using permutation tests based on random reshuffling of trait values across the phylogeny (Blomberg et al., 2003).

To explore whether similar evolutionary pressures have acted independently on different morphological components, we performed phylogenetically independent contrasts (PICs) between the principal components obtained (e.g., snout PC1 vs limb PC1). By including the phylogenetic factor in the regression, we can identify correlations between traits that reflect responses to similar selective pressures rather than inheritance from common ancestors. By doing so, phylogenetic regression not only quantified the strength of trait associations but also provided insight into how natural selection may have independently shaped distinct morphological patterns. We performed a Pearson's test to determine whether a correlation exists between the evolutionary variation described by two different principal components. Trait values were first matched to the phylogeny, then contrasts were calculated under the assumption of a Brownian motion model of trait evolution. Pearson's correlation coefficient was used to assess correlations between contrasts, with phylogenetic linear regression through the origin.

We assessed differences in morphological traits across habitat categories defined in the ecological matrix by performing post-hoc pairwise comparisons using estimated marginal means (emmeans). For each principal component, we first fitted phylogenetic generalised least squares (PGLS) models with habitat category (arboreal, stream-edge, and forest) as a fixed effect. We accounted for phylogenetic non-independence among species by incorporating a Brownian motion correlation structure using the `corBrownian` function. Models were fitted using restricted maximum likelihood (REML).

Pairwise contrasts among habitat categories were then computed using the `emmeans` package in R, yielding estimated differences, standard errors, and associated p-values, with Tukey's method used to adjust for multiple comparisons. This approach allowed us to evaluate whether habitat-related ecological differences significantly influence morphological variation while accounting for shared evolutionary history among species.

2.6 Bioacoustic methods

2.6.1 Sound processing

Recordings were analysed with the Python program “`audio_analysis`” (https://github.com/olivierfriard/audio_analysis.git). The program is organised into modular components (plugins), each designed to perform a specific step of the sound analysis workflow. The analysis pipeline includes: (i) visualization and pre-processing of the audio signal, (ii) segmentation of long recordings into shorter fragments, (iii) detection of acoustic events (notes) based on the amplitude envelope and peak identification (Figure 23), and (iv) extraction of quantitative parameters from individual notes, such as duration, peak number, and spectral features (Figure 24). The modular organisation allows flexible and semi-automatic processing of large audio datasets, and it also allows users to supervise and change the controlling parameters at each stage of the analysis.

Figure 23 - Interface of the "Find peaks" function of the Python programme "audio_analysis", showing the notes detection of a *Gephyromantis cornutus* recording.

Figure 24 – Oscillogram with detected peaks of a *Gephyromantis cornutus* note.

2.6.2 Operational definitions for acoustic parameters

The terminology of frog vocalisations can hardly be unequivocal, especially due to the complexity and diversity of signals. The vocalisations of the analysed species differ impressively in temporal structure and organisation, as well as in acoustic modalities and incorporating them into a single, overall analysis has been challenging. To classify the different vocalisations and their structures, we adopted a note-centred approach and identified three main structural and hierarchical units: notes, calls, and bouts of calls. Definitions of these units are largely consistent with those proposed by Köhler et al. (2017).

2.6.2.1 Call

We define a “call” as the unit of frog vocalisations, a distinct sound separated from other ones by periods of silence, usually longer than the call itself. Depending on the species, calls can correspond to a single note, where each note is temporarily and structurally isolated and singularly performed (simple calls), or to multiple-note structures (see below). In this second scenario, the call does not necessarily correspond to the repetition of a single note; it can also describe the organisation of two or more distinct notes emitted at regular intervals (complex calls).

2.6.2.2 Note

We define a “note” as the main subunit of a call. In some species (e.g., *G. cornutus* and *G. sculpturatus*), a single note forms the call; in other species, multiple notes, either similar or different in structure, compose the call. Based on the temporal pattern of amplitude modulation, we distinguish two main types of notes: modulated and pulsed notes. In modulated notes, the sound waveform is continuous over time and does not include silent intervals, although its amplitude may vary, showing several peaks. In contrast, pulsed notes are characterised by a discontinuous structure, in which the signal is divided into a series of short sound pulses separated by brief silent intervals.

To quantitatively describe the temporal and spectral characteristics of each note, we identified 12 parameters, as described in Table 3. Each parameter was first computed for

each note and then the average value of each descriptor was calculated at the individual level, obtaining an “average note” for each individual.

Table 3 – Operational definitions for the detected note parameters

Note parameter	Definition
Note peak time (s)	Time instant (in seconds from the recording onset) at which the maximum amplitude of the note occurs
Note period (s)	Time interval between the peaks of two consecutive notes
Note rate (notes·s ⁻¹)	Number of notes per second, defined as the inverse of the note period
Note duration (s)	Temporal duration of the note
Envelope 20 (%)	The percentage of the note duration during which the amplitude envelope exceeds 20% of its peak value
Envelope 50 (%)	The percentage of the note duration during which the amplitude envelope exceeds 50% of its peak value
Envelope 80 (%)	The percentage of the note duration during which the amplitude envelope exceeds 80% of its peak value
Ascending phase (s)	Temporal length between the note onset and the first occurrence at which the envelope reaches 90% of its peak amplitude
Descending phase (s)	Time interval between the last occurrence at which the envelope exceeds 90% of its peak amplitude and note offset
Pulse number	Number of peaks within a note
Pulse rate (pulses·s ⁻¹)	Number of peaks per second
Peak frequency (Hz)	Dominant frequency component of the note spectrum

2.6.2.3 Bout of calls (call series)

We define a “*bout of calls*” as a sequence of temporally clustered calls, in which the intervals between consecutive calls are relatively short compared to the much longer intervals that separate one bout from the next. However, in some species, it is not straightforward to determine whether a sequence should be interpreted as a single call composed of multiple notes or as a bout of single-note calls. This ambiguity arises because the temporal boundary separating these two levels of organisation is not always clear.

For this reason, we avoided defining calls and bouts a priori based on arbitrary criteria. Instead, we quantified variation in temporal structure using continuous variables that describe the pattern of note and call organisation. This approach allows us to capture the full range of variation in signal structure without imposing rigid categorical distinctions.

The procedure used to identify coherent sequences of notes/calls consists in several steps. First, for each individual, we computed a list of timestamps over the duration of the entire recording. Each time value corresponds to the time peak of a single sound unit (either a note of a multiple-note call or a call of a single-note call). The time interval between two successive timestamps correspond to the note/call period and the inverse to the instantaneous note/call rate. Bout identification was performed using a threshold-based procedure.

For each species, we generated two series of candidate thresholds (Δt), ranging from 0.005 s to N times the mean note duration (step = 0.01 s), where N was set at 15 (first series) and 30 (second series). For each threshold, consecutive notes separated by an interval lower than or equal to Δt were assigned to the same bout, producing a partition of the sequence into bouts. As expected, the number of identified bouts decreased monotonically with increasing threshold. For each species, we then selected the lowest threshold that produced the most frequent number of bouts across the explored threshold range, and used this value to define bouts throughout an individual's entire recording.

Once the bouts were defined, we quantitatively described them by calculating several parameters, as shown in Table 4. Notice that some individuals resorted to calling without a clear bout structure. For these animals, whose bouts consisted of a single call, it was not possible to compute many of these descriptors. For each individual, we calculated the mean values of the bout properties, along with the total number of bouts and the number and percentage of calls that were not organised into bouts. Lastly, from the individual means, we calculated the mean value of each parameter for the entire species. We also calculated the percentage of single-note bouts per species and the average bout duration, both of which have been fundamental in distinguishing between species using these two parameters.

Table 4 – Operational definitions for detected bout parameters. Depending on the species, these parameters describe either the sequence of single-note calls within a bout or the sequence of notes in multiple-note calls. For this reason, we used the generic term “sound-unit” instead of “note” or “call”.

Bout parameter	Definition
Peak (s)	Time instant (in seconds from the recording onset) at which the maximum amplitude of the note occurs.
Sound-unit period (s)	Time interval between two consecutive peaks within a bout
Bout interval	Time interval between the last peak of the preceding bout and the first peak of the following bout.
Sound-units per bout	Number of peaks per second, defined as the inverse of the note period.
Intensity variation index (IVI)	Sum of the Δ of intensity between the calls of the bout. If there is an increase/decrease of intensity within the bout, the index value will relevantly differ from 0, whereas values close to 0 describe bouts not characterised by an incoherent intensity pattern. This parameter is calculated only on bouts with more than two notes.

2.6.3 Statistical analyses

As described for the morphometric dataset, also for the acoustic dataset, we carried out descriptive analyses to describe the patterns of acoustic variation (e.g., PCA) both within- and between species, and inferential statistical tests to analyse the effect of temperature and body size on call acoustic properties and how these effects vary in relation to the ecology and the phylogenetic position of the species.

Phylogenetic analyses of note spectral traits were performed on a subgroup comprising species with at least four sampled individuals to increase the statistical power of the analyses. We therefore fitted a model with species as a fixed effect, aiming to calculate adjusted means for each species, remove the size factor (which was previously observed not to contain phylogenetic signal), and investigate whether any evolutionary lineages showed a tendency toward an increase or decrease in dominant frequency. Using the *emmeans* function, we obtained the adjusted means of the log-transformed dominant frequency and their standard errors. In further phylogenetic analyses, we used only Note type A of *Spinomantis aglavei*, due to the similarity in their dominant frequencies.

3 Results

3.1 Individual recognition

The abundance and distribution of frogs across forest habitats (stream edges, ponds, trees) made individual recaptures possible, but unlikely. This was confirmed by non-invasive recognition methods based on comparisons of ventral and subgular patterns in the collected specimens, which revealed only a few recaptures within our sample. Specifically, recaptures involved two *Guibemantis depressiceps* specimens (Figure 25) and an individual of *Boophis burgeri*, which was captured twice. No other correspondence has been detected, although it may have occurred and gone unnoticed. Even in the absence of confirmatory genetic data, we are confident that the sampling approach adopted in this study has a low risk of recapture and can thus be applied to further studies in the rainforest.

Figure 25 – Spot dispositions on the abdomen of three specimens of *Guibemantis depressiceps*. A and B are resamples of the same individual, as recognisable by spot disposition. C is a different individual, as recognisable by the different abdominal pattern.

3.2 Collected sample

We obtained morphometric data for 373 individuals from 36 species. Most individuals belonged to the family Mantellidae, but we also collected data from specimens included in other families, including *Plethodontohyla* spp., *Anodonthyla boulengeri*, *Rhombophryne alluaudi*, *Platypelis babouri*, and *Heterixalus betsileo*. Data of extra-mantellid species were not included in this thesis, but we hope they may be useful for further studies. Species represented by fewer than three individuals were excluded from the analyses (*Boophis goudotii*, *Boophis pyrrhus*, *Mantidactylus femoralis*, *Mantidactylus zipperi*, *Mantidactylus argenteus*), as well as samples of females (8 females in total, 2 per species for *B. madagascariensis*, *G. sculpturatus*, *G. malagasius* and *S. aglavei*). Sample sizes varied across species due to factors such as encounter rates and the ease of recording and capturing individuals. Our final dataset counts 345 individuals of 24 species; the most represented genus is *Gephyromantis* (103 individuals), followed by *Boophis* (101), *Mantidactylus* (56), *Spinomantis* (53), and *Guibemantis* (32). At the species level, the most collected species are *Gephyromantis cornutus* (39), *Spinomantis aglavei* (38), *Gephyromantis sculpturatus* (35), and *Boophis boehmei* (33). This sample includes species not previously listed among the amphibians in the rainforest of Maromizaha, including *Boophis tasymena*, *Boophis erythroactylus*, *Mantidactylus albofrenatus* and *Spinomantis phantasticus*. The list of sampled individuals per species included in the final dataset is shown in Table 5.

Table 5 - Resume of the number of individuals photographed and recorded for each species in the final dataset, ordered alphabetically per genus and grouped per subgenus/subgroup.

Species	Subgenus/subgroup	Genus	Photographed	Recorded
<i>B. grandisonae</i>	NA	<i>Blommersia</i>	3	0
<i>B. albilabris</i>	<i>Albilabris gr.</i>	<i>Boophis</i>	9	9
<i>B. boehmei</i>	<i>Goudoti gr.</i>	<i>Boophis</i>	33	33
<i>B. burgeri</i>	<i>Goudoti gr.</i>	<i>Boophis</i>	6	6
<i>B. madagascariensis</i>	<i>Goudoti gr.</i>	<i>Boophis</i>	18	16
<i>B. reticulatus</i>	<i>Goudoti gr.</i>	<i>Boophis</i>	11	11
<i>B. erythroductylus</i>	<i>Rappiodes gr.</i>	<i>Boophis</i>	4	3
<i>B. tasymena</i>	<i>Rappiodes gr.</i>	<i>Boophis</i>	3	3
<i>B. picturatus</i>	<i>Majori gr.</i>	<i>Boophis</i>	5	5
<i>B. aff. sibilans</i>	<i>Albipunctatus gr.</i>	<i>Boophis</i>	9	8
<i>G. cornutus</i>	<i>Duboimantis</i>	<i>Gephyromantis</i>	39	39
<i>G. sculpturatus</i>	<i>Duboimantis</i>	<i>Gephyromantis</i>	35	35
<i>G. malagasius</i>	<i>Laurentomantis</i>	<i>Gephyromantis</i>	18	18
<i>G. bouleengeri</i>	<i>Gephyromantis</i>	<i>Gephyromantis</i>	11	11
<i>G. liber</i>	<i>Pandanusicola</i>	<i>Guibemantis</i>	10	9
<i>G. depressiceps</i>	<i>Guibemantis</i>	<i>Guibemantis</i>	19	19
<i>G. tornieri</i>	<i>Guibemantis</i>	<i>Guibemantis</i>	3	3
<i>M. albofrenatus</i>	<i>Chonomantis</i>	<i>Mantidactylus</i>	11	11
<i>M. melanopleura</i>	<i>Chonomantis</i>	<i>Mantidactylus</i>	10	10
<i>M. opiparis</i>	<i>Chonomantis</i>	<i>Mantidactylus</i>	14	14
<i>M. betsileanus</i>	<i>Brygoomantis</i>	<i>Mantidactylus</i>	12	12
<i>M. biporus</i>	<i>Brygoomantis</i>	<i>Mantidactylus</i>	9	4
<i>S. aglavei</i>	NA	<i>Spinomantis</i>	38	38
<i>S. phantasticus</i>	NA	<i>Spinomantis</i>	15	15
TOTAL			345	332

3.3 Morphometry results

3.3.1 Repeatability

Table 6 shows the mean repeatability estimates and their credibility intervals (CIs) for the x- and y-landmark coordinates. The mean repeatability was 0.904. Most of the landmarks (71%) show repeatability higher than 0.9 and only one landmark (the cervical y-coordinate) has repeatability lower than 0.6. This means that the among-individual

variation was always much greater than the within-individual variation. We conclude that our landmark configuration is appropriate to analyse shape variation in this group of frogs.

Table 6 - Posterior mode and credibility intervals (CI) of repeatability estimates of the x- and y-coordinates of landmarks.

Landmarks	X-coordinates		Y-coordinates	
	Posterior mode	CI	Posterior mode	CI
LHead1	0.974	(0.555, 0.899)	0.786	(0.555, 0.899)
LHead2	0.805	(0.751, 0.951)	0.912	(0.751, 0.951)
LHead3	0.929	(0.780, 0.960)	0.919	(0.780, 0.960)
RHead1	0.903	(0.632, 0.921)	0.829	(0.632, 0.921)
RHead2	0.944	(0.820, 0.966)	0.895	(0.820, 0.966)
RHead3	0.963	(0.587, 0.910)	0.728	(0.587, 0.910)
LNostril	0.975	(0.704, 0.943)	0.902	(0.704, 0.943)
RNostril	0.985	(0.674, 0.929)	0.855	(0.674, 0.929)
LMidEye	0.880	(0.524, 0.887)	0.685	(0.524, 0.887)
RMidEye	0.927	(0.500, 0.881)	0.710	(0.500, 0.881)
Cervical	0.949	(0.229, 0.765)	0.512	(0.229, 0.765)
LArmPit	0.959	(0.788, 0.959)	0.845	(0.788, 0.959)
LElb	0.958	(0.948, 0.991)	0.963	(0.948, 0.991)
LMCarp	0.922	(0.952, 0.992)	0.969	(0.952, 0.992)
LFingHand4	0.971	(0.955, 0.992)	0.990	(0.955, 0.992)
LFingHand3	0.980	(0.929, 0.987)	0.946	(0.929, 0.987)
LFingHand2	0.875	(0.792, 0.960)	0.937	(0.792, 0.960)
LFingHand1	0.906	(0.671, 0.931)	0.823	(0.671, 0.931)
RArmPit	0.940	(0.657, 0.927)	0.750	(0.657, 0.927)
RElb	0.958	(0.848, 0.974)	0.874	(0.848, 0.974)
RMCarp	0.924	(0.868, 0.977)	0.934	(0.868, 0.977)
RFingHand4	0.973	(0.875, 0.978)	0.949	(0.875, 0.978)
RFingHand3	0.959	(0.892, 0.980)	0.932	(0.892, 0.980)
RFingHand2	0.941	(0.846, 0.972)	0.877	(0.846, 0.972)
RFingHand1	0.938	(0.893, 0.981)	0.975	(0.893, 0.981)
LKnee	0.991	(0.901, 0.982)	0.960	(0.901, 0.982)
LTar	0.944	(0.921, 0.986)	0.980	(0.921, 0.986)
LToe	0.930	(0.922, 0.987)	0.982	(0.922, 0.987)
RKnee	0.983	(0.895, 0.982)	0.952	(0.895, 0.982)
RTar	0.816	(0.908, 0.985)	0.966	(0.908, 0.985)
RToe	0.639	(0.965, 0.994)	0.984	(0.965, 0.994)

3.3.2 Patterns of morphometric variation

3.3.2.1 Classic morphometrics: PCA

Canonical loadings of the principal component analysis performed on log-transformed morphometric parameters are shown in Table 7. Scatterplots showing species distribution across PC1, PC2 and PC3 are shown below (Figure 26, Figure 27). The first three components account for 98.6% of the total variance: 95.1% by PC1, 2.2% by PC2, and 1.4% by PC3. The first principal component is a size component, as all variables load positively and with similar magnitudes on this component (loadings range from 0.305 to 0.319). PC2 contrasts the forelimbs (including digits II, III and IV) with the hindlimbs, with high scores of this component corresponding to species with proportionally short posterior limbs relative to anterior ones. PC3 describes a trade-off between the humerus and the digits except digit I (-0.044), with high scores on this component corresponding to species with proportionally short humeri and longer hand digits (digit III: 0.310; digit IV: 0.378). PC2 and PC3 describe differences in limb proportions and can be considered indicators of overall shape differences.

Table 7 - Canonical loadings and percentage of variance explained by the first three principal components of log-transformed morphometric parameters.

Logarithmic segment	PC1	PC2	PC3
ln SVL	0.319	-0.138	0.024
ln Humerus	0.305	0.292	-0.816
ln Radius	0.319	0.188	0.058
ln Digit IV	0.317	0.293	0.378
ln Digit III	0.317	0.349	0.310
ln Digit II	0.319	0.325	0.153
ln Digit I	0.317	-0.044	-0.225
ln Femur	0.316	-0.446	0.103
ln Tibial	0.314	-0.489	0.043
ln Foot	0.319	-0.325	-0.060
Explained variance (%)	95.060	2.117	1.427
Cumulative variance (%)	95.060	97.177	98.604

Figure 26 is a plot of size (PC1) against limb shape (PC2), revealing substantial size variability among the sampled species, with species distributed along the entire PC1 axis. This dispersal highlights three groups: large frogs with high PC1 scores (*B. albilabris*: 8.52; *B. madagascariensis*: 4.33), medium-sized species with PC1 scores ranging from -2 to 2, and smaller frogs on the left side of the plot. PC2, describing the contrast between anterior and posterior limbs, seems more genus-related, with lower intra-genus variability and more similar limb proportions (PC2 scores range: *Boophis* spp. [-0.5, 0.25]; *Spinomantis* spp. [0.25, 0.75]; *Mantidactylus* spp. [-0.5, 0.5]), except for the genus *Gephyromantis*. The two species of the subgenus *Duboimantis*, *G. sculpturatus* and *G. cornutus*, markedly differ on this trait (*G. cornutus*: -0.16; *G. sculpturatus*: 0.85), with *G. sculpturatus* having relatively longer posterior limbs than the anterior ones, whereas this pattern is not observed in *G. cornutus*.

Figure 26 – Scatterplot showing the distribution of the sampled species along the first two principal components calculated on morphometric distances using the classic approach. Each dot represents an individual and the legend on the right lists species with their corresponding colour codes. Species labels represent the centroid of each species individuals dispersal.

In Figure 27, PC1 is plotted against PC3, which mainly describes variation in forelimb shape (relative proportions of humerus and hand finger length). Within the genus *Boophis*, we observe high variability along PC3, which appears to reflect size differences revealed by PC1: larger and smaller species tend to have lower PC3 scores (below 0.5), whereas the medium-sized group of *Boophis* tends to have shorter humeri relative to the hand digits (scores above 0.5). Intra-genus differences are less pronounced in all other considered genera represented by multiple species (*Gephyromantis*, *Guibemantis*, *Mantidactylus*) except for *Spinomantis*, where the two species seem to differ in these anterior limb proportions (*S. aglavei*: -0.24; *S. phantasticus*: 0.25).

Figure 27 - Scatterplot showing the distribution of the sampled species along PC1 and PC3 calculated on morphometric distances using the classic approach. Each dot represents an individual and the legend on the right lists species with their corresponding colour codes. Species labels represent the centroid of each species

3.3.2.2 Geometric morphometrics PCA - Limbs

The PCA of Procrustes-aligned limb coordinates showed that the first three principal components accounted for 90.77% of total shape variance (PC1 = 57.66%, PC2 = 24.37%, PC3 = 8.74%). Principal components, with their eigenvalues and the percentage of explained variance, are reported in Table 8.

Table 8 – Eigenvalues, explained and cumulative variance for each of the first three principal components calculated on Procrustes-aligned limb coordinates.

Principal component	Eigenvalue	Variance explained (%)	Cumulative variance (%)
PC1	0.00139	57.657	57.657
PC2	0.00059	24.365	82.022
PC3	0.00021	8.742	90.765

Shape variation along the principal components is visualised using thin-plate deformation grids. The first principal component (PC1), accounting for 57.66% of the total shape variance, represents the main axis of shape variation. Thin-plate deformation grids for PC1 (Figure 28) show the transition from specimens with a greater distance between the snout tip and the cervical region, shorter vertebral columns and shorter fingers, especially for digit III and digit IV, to specimens showing the opposite pattern.

Figure 28 – Thin-plate deformation grids for the first principal component calculated performing a PCA on Procrustes-aligned limb subgroup landmarks. Grid on the left corresponds to lowest scores of PC1, whereas the one on the right corresponds to highest scores of PC1.

The second principal component accounts for 24.37% of the total shape variance. Thin-plate deformation grids (Figure 29) show the transition from specimens with longer tibia/fibula segments and anterior limbs positioned closer to the head (left) to specimens characterised by shorter tibias/fibulas and a reorganisation of forelimbs, probably in association with a proportionally larger head (right).

Figure 29 - Thin-plate deformation grids for the second principal component calculated by performing a PCA on Procrustes-aligned limb subgroup landmarks. The grid on the left corresponds to the lowest PC2 scores, whereas the one on the right corresponds to the highest PC2 scores.

The third principal component accounts for 8.74% of the total shape variance. Thin-plate deformation grids (Figure 30) show the transition from specimens with a lower ratio between digits and radius lengths and a longer distance between the cervical region and the vent (left) to specimens showing elongated digits and a shorter distance between the cervical and the vent (right).

Figure 30 - Thin-plate deformation grids for the third principal component calculated by performing a PCA on Procrustes-aligned limb subgroup landmarks. The grid on the left corresponds to the lowest PC3 scores, whereas the one on the right corresponds to the highest PC3 scores.

Scatterplot in Figure 31 shows the distribution of the sampled species along the first two principal components. The first principal component seems to be associated with the tendency of each species to live under arboreal conditions, since arboreal genera *Boophis*, *Guibemantis* and *Spinomantis* all position on the right half of the plot (PC1 scores above 0), whereas scores below zero for PC1 are associated with all terrestrial genera (*Blommersia*, *Gephyromantis* and *Mantidactylus*). On the contrary, PC2 seems to be associated with head shape (and potential limb rearrangement) more than ecological habits. *M. biporus*, whose head shape is the closest to the one interpretable in the positive extreme thin-plate deformation grid of PC2, is separated from all other species, showing the highest PC2 scores (> 0.75), followed by other representatives of the genus *Mantidactylus* (*M. betsileanus* and *M. albofrenatus*, both with PC2 scores above 0.25).

Figure 31 - Scatterplot showing the distribution of the sampled species along PC1 and PC2 calculated on Procrustes-aligned coordinates of the limb subgroup of landmarks. Each dot corresponds to an individual. List of species with corresponding colour code is on the right side of the plot. Species labels represent the centroid of each species individuals dispersal.

The scatterplot in Figure 32 shows the distribution of the sampled species along PC1 and PC3, illustrating species distribution along the third principal component. High scores for PC3 are found in the species of the genus *Guibemantis* and in a complex of species from different genera (*G. malagasius*, *B. grandisonae*, *M. albofrenatus* and *S. phantasticus*), all with PC3 scores above 0. In contrast, *M. biporus* and a group of species of the genus *Boophis* (*B. aff. sibilans*, *B. tasymena* and *B. erythroductylus*) have the lowest scores for PC3 (below -0.015). This component's described variation in shape groups closely the different genera, except for the genus *Gephyromantis*.

Figure 32 - Scatterplot showing the distribution of the sampled species along PC1 and PC3 calculated on Procrustes-aligned coordinates of the limb subgroup of landmarks. Each dot corresponds to an individual. The list of species with corresponding colour code is on the right side of the plot. Species labels represent the centroid of each species individuals dispersal.

3.3.2.3 Geometric morphometrics PCA - Head

The first three principal components of the PCA of Procrustes-aligned head coordinates accounted for 91.48% of total shape variance (PC1 = 63.80%, PC2 = 21.10%, PC3 = 6.57%). The principal components, along with their respective eigenvalues and the percentage of explained variance, are reported in Table 9.

Table 9 - Eigenvalues, explained and cumulative variance for each of the first three principal components calculated on Procrustes-aligned head coordinates.

Principal component	Eigenvalue	Variance explained (%)	Cumulative variance (%)
PC1	0.00373	63.803	63.803
PC2	0.00123	21.101	84.905
PC3	0.00038	6.572	91.478

The first principal component (PC1), accounting for 63.80% of the total shape variance, represents the main axis of shape variation. Thin-plate deformation grids (Figure 33) show the transition from specimens with higher distance between the tip of the snout and the cervical and minor distance between the Head3 landmarks, placed in the point of conjunction between the head and the shoulder, in which head elongation occurs along the sagittal plane, to ones with minor distance between the tip of the snout and the cervical and higher distance between the Head3 landmarks, in which the head enlarges along the frontal plane.

Figure 33 - Thin-plate deformation grids for the first principal component calculated by performing a PCA on Procrustes-aligned head subgroup landmarks. The grid on the left corresponds to the lowest PC1 scores, whereas the one on the right corresponds to the highest PC1 scores.

The second principal component (PC2), accounting for 21.10% of the total shape variance, captures variation in eye position, as indicated by the positions of the MidEye landmarks, which correspond to the innermost margin of the eye.

Thin-plate deformation grids for PC2 (Figure 34) show the transition from specimens with frontally positioned eyes to specimens with laterally positioned eyes.

Figure 34 - Thin-plate deformation grids for the second principal component calculated by performing a PCA on Procrustes-aligned head subgroup landmarks. The grid on the left corresponds to the lowest PC2 scores, whereas the one on the right corresponds to the highest PC2 scores.

The third principal component (PC3), accounting for 6.57% of the total shape variance, describes the ratio between eye and head sizes and can be interpreted by the positions of the Head1 and Head2 landmarks, corresponding to the proximal and distal eye points relative to the snout tip. Thin-plate deformation grids for PC3 (Figure 35) illustrate the transition from specimens with a high eye-to-head ratio to specimens with a lower ratio.

Figure 35 - Thin-plate deformation grids for the third principal component calculated by performing a PCA on Procrustes-aligned head subgroup landmarks. The grid on the left corresponds to the lowest PC3 scores, whereas the one on the right corresponds to the highest PC3 scores.

The scatterplot in Figure 37 shows the distribution of the sampled species along PC1 and PC3. The third principal component, corresponding to the eye/head ratio, is less consistent within each genus considered. Both species of the subgenus *Brygoomantis* (*M. betsileanus* and *M. biporus*) have high scores for the third principal component (> 0.03), indicating a lower eye/head ratio, as well as a complex of species of the genus *Boophis* (*B. albilabris*, *B. erythroductylus* and *B. tasymena*) and *G. malagasius*. Lower scores of the third principal component are found in *B. grandisonae* (< 0.02), in a complex of *Boophis* species (*B. burgeri*, *B. reticulatus* and *B. picturatus*), in *M. albofrenatus* and in *G. liber*.

Figure 37 - Scatterplot showing the distribution of the sampled species along PC1 and PC3 calculated on Procrustes-aligned coordinates of the head subgroup of landmarks. Each dot corresponds to an individual. List of species with corresponding colour code is on the right side of the plot.

3.3.3 Phylogeny

The list of species uploaded to timetree.org returned their phylogeny (Figure 38) and the Newick file (.nwk) used for phylogenetic statistical analysis in R. As previously mentioned, due to the lack of genetic data for two species (*M. albofrenatus* and *S. phantasticus*), the Newick tree was subsequently integrated with these species. The phylogenetic tree of the considered species highlights relevant splits within the phylogeny of these two subfamilies (Mantellinae and Boophinae). Within Mantellinae, an initial split led to the separation of *Spinomantis*, *Guibemantis*, and *Blommersia*. The most recent splits (approximately 10 MYA) affect *Guibemantis tornieri* and *Guibemantis depressiceps*, *Mantidactylus opiparis* and *Mantidactylus melanopleura* and *Boophis tasymena* and *Boophis erythroductylus*. *Boophis burgeri* and *Boophis reticulatus* also share a relatively recent common ancestor.

Figure 38 – Phylogenetic tree provided by the website *timetree.org*. Below is reported the geologic timescale to interpret branch lengths.

3.3.3.1 Blomberg's K and Pagel's λ

Phylogenetic signal of the principal components (PCs) derived from overall classic morphometrics and separate analyses of head and body traits (geometric morphometrics), using Blomberg's K and Pagel's λ , is shown in Table 10.

Table 10 – Phylogenetic signals K and λ and p-values for each principal component.

	Blomberg's K		Pagel's λ	
	Phylogenetic signal K	p-value	Phylogenetic signal λ	p-value
PC1	0.575	0.192	0.999	0.097
PC2	1.234	0.004	0.999	0.002
PC3	2.844	0.001	0.999	<0.001
PC1 limbs	1.807	0.001	0.999	<0.001
PC2 limbs	1.169	0.008	0.999	0.013
PC3 limbs	1.018	0.015	0.925	0.005
PC1 head	2.061	0.001	0.999	<0.001
PC2 head	1.345	0.005	0.999	0.003
PC3 head	0.834	0.033	0.999	0.022

Regarding the classic approach, PC1 showed a moderate phylogenetic signal ($K = 0.575$, $p = 0.192$; $\lambda = 0.999$, $p = 0.097$), indicating a non-significant influence of phylogeny on size variation. In contrast, PC2 exhibited a strong phylogenetic signal ($K = 1.234$, $p = 0.004$; $\lambda = 0.999$, $p = 0.002$) as well as PC3 ($K = 2.844$, $p = 0.001$; $\lambda = 0.999$, $p < 0.001$). Every principal component describing limb shape showed significant phylogenetic signal, suggesting that limb variation is largely shaped by evolutionary history. PC1 of head morphology exhibited a strong phylogenetic signal ($K = 2.061$, $p = 0.001$; $\lambda = 0.999$, $p < 0.001$), reflecting high conservation along the phylogeny. PC2 ($K = 1.345$, $p = 0.005$; $\lambda = 0.999$, $p = 0.003$) and PC3 ($K = 0.834$, $p = 0.033$; $\lambda = 0.999$, $p = 0.022$) of head morphology displayed weaker but still significant phylogenetic influence. In general, these results show that the first principal components, except for the classic approach, are strongly phylogenetically conserved, whereas PC2 and PC3 are less tightly linked to phylogenetic relationships.

Within Boophinae (results in Table 11), Blomberg's K showed moderate to strong phylogenetic signal for several principal components, suggesting trait conservation. On the contrary, Pagel's λ was often not significant, likely due to the limited power to detect phylogenetic trace within this smaller subgroup. In fact, fewer taxa, depth and phylogenetic contrast result in lower accountability for these tests, with Blomberg's K stronger and more accountable than Pagel's λ on smaller trees due to its trait randomisation. Blomberg's K showed a strong phylogenetic signal for PC1 (K = 1.248, p = 0.018) and PC3 (K = 1.224, p = 0.043) of the classic approach. Limbs' second principal component has a strong phylogenetic trace (K = 1.318, p = 0.006; λ = 1.481, p = 0.005), while the third principal component has a weaker but present phylogenetic trace (λ = 1.476, p = 0.041). Among the PCs describing head shape variation, PC3 (describing the eye/head ratio) has a significant phylogenetic trace (K = 1.265, p = 0.034), suggesting that within Boophinae this ratio is phylogenetically conserved.

Table 11 - Phylogenetic signals K and λ and *p-values* for each principal component calculated on the subset Boophinae.

Boophinae	Blomberg's K		Pagel's λ	
	Phylogenetic signal K	p-value	Phylogenetic signal λ	p-value
PC1	1.248	0.018	1.370	0.082
PC2	0.881	0.362	0.365	0.574
PC3	1.224	0.043	1.364	0.090
PC1 limbs	0.887	0.310	0.246	0.857
PC2 limbs	1.318	0.006	1.481	0.005
PC3 limbs	1.113	0.074	1.476	0.041
PC1 head	0.970	0.162	0.725	0.611
PC2 head	0.932	0.271	<0.001	1
PC3 head	1.265	0.034	1.211	0.099

Within Mantellinae (Table 12), a larger subset (more species) enabled assessment of the phylogenetic signal for several principal components using both Blomberg's K and Pagel's λ . The first two principal components obtained by the classic approach showed a strong phylogenetic signal (PC1: K = 0.968, p = 0.041; PC2: K = 1.389, p = 0.002; λ = 0.999, p = 0.005), while the impact of phylogeny is weaker on PC3 (K = 0.861, p = 0.058). Every principal component describing limb shape shows a significant phylogenetic trace, stronger for PC1 (K = 1.826, p = 0.001; λ = 0.999, p = 0.001) and weaker for PC2 and PC3 (PC2 limbs: K = 0.934, p = 0.013; PC3 limbs: K = 0.888, p = 0.049). PC1 of head shape displayed strong phylogenetic signal (K = 1.324, p = 0.001; λ = 0.999, p = 0.012), while PC2 head showed no significant results for the applied tests. Blomberg's K also detected a phylogenetic signal in PC3 head (K = 0.941, p = 0.039).

Table 12 - Phylogenetic signals K and λ and p-values for each principal component calculated on the subset Mantellinae.

Mantellinae	Blomberg's K		Pagel's λ	
	Phylogenetic signal K	p-value	Phylogenetic signal λ	p-value
PC1	0.968	0.041	0.999	0.139
PC2	1.389	0.002	0.999	0.005
PC3	0.861	0.058	0.674	0.168
PC1 limbs	1.826	0.001	0.999	0.001
PC2 limbs	0.934	0.013	0.999	0.107
PC3 limbs	0.888	0.049	0.810	0.199
PC1 head	1.324	0.001	0.999	0.012
PC2 head	0.710	0.223	<0.001	1
PC3 head	0.941	0.039	0.999	0.130

3.3.3.2 Phylogenetically independent contrasts

Results for the Pearson's correlation tests are summarised in Table 13. Correlation tests between principal components from classic and geometric PCAs reveal significant covariances between specific axes. In particular, PC2 applied to the classic approach exhibited a strong correlation with the PCs describing limb shape variation (PC1 limbs: r = 0.589, p = 0.003; PC2 limbs: r = 0.413, p = 0.050; PC3 limbs: r = 0.560, p = 0.005). Also, the classic approach's PC3 showed a strong correlation with PC1 limbs (r = 0.502,

$p = 0.015$). These correlations were not unexpected, since PCA performed on the classic approach, except for PC1 describing the size factor, especially captures differences in limb proportions. Pearson's tests on PCs limbs and PCs head exhibited a correlation between these components, both with concordant and discordant trends (PC1 limbs vs PC1 head: $r = 0.580$, $p = 0.004$; PC2 limbs vs PC2 head: $r = -0.521$, $p = 0.011$; PC2 limbs vs PC3 head: $r = 0.505$, $p = 0.014$). Not every tested couple of principal components showed a significant correlation, suggesting that only specific axes were integrated.

Table 13 – Correlation coefficients (r) and p -values for each performed correlation test.

Variable	PC1 limbs		PC2 limbs		PC3 limbs		PC1 head		PC2 head		PC3 head	
	r	p	r	p	r	p	r	p	r	p	r	p
PC1	0.192	0.381	-0.288	0.183	-0.039	0.860	0.104	0.638	0.121	0.584	0.110	0.618
PC2	0.589	0.003	0.413	0.050	0.560	0.005	0.102	0.642	-0.262	0.228	0.045	0.840
PC3	0.502	0.015	-0.158	0.473	0.355	0.096	0.270	0.212	-0.311	0.148	-0.312	0.148
PC1 limbs							0.580	0.004	-0.110	0.618	-0.206	0.346
PC2 limbs							0.006	0.978	-0.521	0.011	0.505	0.014
PC3 limbs							-0.331	0.123	-0.027	0.904	-0.195	0.372

3.3.3.3 Post-hoc pairwise contrasts

Post hoc pairwise contrasts from *emmeans* are summarised in Table 14. These contrasts reveal no significant differences in principal components resulting from the classic approach, nor in those describing head shape, which does not differ significantly among arboreal, stream-edge and forestal species across any examined principal components. Limb morphology, in contrast, shows habitat-related differentiation. Both PC1 and PC2 describing limbs shape exhibit significant differences especially for stream edge species,

which differ both from arboreal and forestal species in limb proportions (PC1limbs: Arboreal-Stream edge, $p = 0.024$; Stream edge-forestal, $p = 0.043$; PC2limbs: Arboreal-Stream edge, $p = 0.040$; Stream edge-forestal, $p = 0.014$), while no significant differences is detected for PC3 of limb shape.

Table 14 – Estimates, standard errors (SE) and p values of each guild contrast for each considered principal component.

Variable	Contrast	Estimate	SE	p value
PC1	Arboreal - Stream edge	4.950	2.720	0.189
PC1	Arboreal - Forestal	2.800	2.020	0.368
PC1	Stream edge - Forestal	-2.150	2.440	0.658
PC2	Arboreal - Stream edge	0.108	0.293	0.928
PC2	Arboreal - Forestal	-0.011	0.218	0.999
PC2	Stream edge - Forestal	-0.119	0.263	0.894
PC3	Arboreal - Stream edge	0.498	0.232	0.105
PC3	Arboreal - Forestal	-0.019	0.172	0.993
PC3	Stream edge - Forestal	-0.518	0.208	0.054
PC1 limbs	Arboreal - Stream edge	0.055	0.019	0.024
PC1 limbs	Arboreal - Forestal	0.011	0.014	0.736
PC1 limbs	Stream edge - Forestal	-0.044	0.017	0.044
PC2 limbs	Arboreal - Stream edge	-0.044	0.017	0.040
PC2 limbs	Arboreal - Forestal	0.003	0.013	0.976
PC2 limbs	Stream edge - Forestal	0.047	0.015	0.014
PC3 limbs	Arboreal - Stream edge	0.005	0.010	0.870
PC3 limbs	Arboreal - Forestal	-0.006	0.008	0.697
PC3 limbs	Stream edge - Forestal	-0.012	0.009	0.445
PC1 head	Arboreal - Stream edge	0.071	0.035	0.128
PC1 head	Arboreal - Forestal	0.017	0.026	0.784
PC1 head	Stream edge - Forestal	-0.054	0.031	0.222
PC2 head	Arboreal - Stream edge	0.022	0.016	0.362
PC2 head	Arboreal - Forestal	-0.003	0.012	0.957
PC2 head	Stream edge - Forestal	-0.026	0.014	0.198
PC3 head	Arboreal - Stream edge	-0.014	0.017	0.671
PC3 head	Arboreal - Forestal	-0.002	0.012	0.991
PC3 head	Stream edge - Forestal	0.013	0.015	0.677

3.4 Bioacoustics results

3.4.1 Analysed sample

We analysed the recordings of 20 species representing 5 genera of the family Mantellidae. Some species were not included in the analyses because of small samples or low quality recordings, due to the impact of weather conditions or the relevant distance occurring between the recorder and the individual (*B. tasymena*, *B. erythrodactylus*).

The analysed sample includes 6 species of *Boophis* (*B. albilabris*, *B. boehmei*, *B. burgeri*, *B. picturatus*, *B. reticulatus* and *B. aff. sibilans*), 4 species representing the genus *Gephyromantis* (*G. boulengeri*, *G. cornutus*, *G. malagasius* and *G. sculpturatus*), 3 *Guibemantis* (*G. depressiceps*, *G. liber* and *G. tornieri*), 5 species of *Mantidactylus* (*M. albofrenatus*, *M. betsileanus*, *M. biporus*, *M. melanopleura* and *M. opiparis*) and two species of *Spinomantis* (*S. aglavei* and *S. phantasticus*). The most sampled species in terms of recorded specimens are *B. boehmei* (34), *G. cornutus* (40), *G. sculpturatus* (40) and *S. aglavei* (41); the less sampled species are *G. tornieri* (3), *M. biporus* (3), *B. albilabris* (5) and *B. picturatus* (5).

Resume of recording samples for each species are shown in Table 15.

Table 15 – Number of recorded individuals per species.

Species	Recorded specimens
<i>Boophis</i>	
<i>Boophis albilabris</i>	5
<i>Boophis boehmei</i>	34
<i>Boophis burgeri</i>	11
<i>Boophis picturatus</i>	5
<i>Boophis reticulatus</i>	6
<i>Boophis aff. sibilans</i>	9
<i>Gephyromantis</i>	
<i>Gephyromantis boulengeri</i>	11
<i>Gephyromantis cornutus</i>	40
<i>Gephyromantis malagasius</i>	21
<i>Gephyromantis sculpturatus</i>	40
<i>Guibemantis</i>	
<i>Guibemantis depressiceps</i>	21
<i>Guibemantis liber</i>	9
<i>Guibemantis tornieri</i>	3
<i>Mantidactylus</i>	
<i>Mantidactylus albofrenatus</i>	11
<i>Mantidactylus betsileanus</i>	15
<i>Mantidactylus biporus</i>	3
<i>Mantidactylus melanopleura</i>	10
<i>Mantidactylus opiparis</i>	15
<i>Spinomantis</i>	
<i>Spinomantis aglavei</i>	41
<i>Spinomantis phantasticus</i>	21

Three species of our dataset emit two note types that differ in all considered parameters and we chose to treat the two types as two distinct and independent subgroups in further analyses. This involved *S. aglavei*, which emits two distinct types of notes: one reminding of a “metallic” sound (Note A), usually organised in series, and a second type, defined as “croak” (Note B), emitted alone, never in series. Similarly, *B. aff. sibilans* emits two different whistling calls, one appearing on the oscillogram as a single pulse (Note A) and a second one composed of five clearly distinct different pulses (Note B) (see Figure 39). In this case, due to the high morphological and bioacoustics similarity occurring within the *B. albipunctatus* species complex, we decided to consider only the first note type, of which we had more samples. A similar decision was taken when considering the calling of *B. reticulatus*, whose notes are extremely different when performed singularly (Note A) than when emitted in series (Note B), so we analysed them separately. In other species of the genus *Boophis*, we still noticed a large variation in some note properties, such as note

duration, and the number of pulses. However, in these cases, variation was continuous and appeared to depend on how calling was structured: when notes were emitted in fast series, they were typically shorter and had fewer pulses; in contrast, when they were emitted alone, they were of longer duration and with higher number of pulses or peaks. In these cases, we adopted the parsimonious decision to consider all these variants as belonging to the same call type.

Figure 39 – Two note types of *B. aff. Sibilans* recorded. A: Note type A, consisting of a single pulse. B: Note type B, consisting of five pulses.

3.4.2 Analyses of acoustic variation: the note

Table 16 shows the descriptive statistics of all the acoustic properties describing the note structure. For species with two note types,

Among the acoustic properties considered, Envelope20, Envelope50 and Envelope80 were chosen to describe the pattern of amplitude modulation of a note. For this reason, we first run a PCA on these three properties and extracted the first principal component, which explained 84.61% of total variation (Table 17). The canonical loadings are similar in magnitude and sign, suggesting that low PC1 scores correspond to highly modulated notes.

In Figure 40, the boxplot of PC1 is shown. From this distribution, three distinct groups emerge: i) species with PC1 medians lower than 2 (N = 5); ii) species with the median values of PC1 comprised between -1 and 0.5 (N = 8); iii) species with median values greater than 1 (N = 9).

Table 16 – Descriptive statistics of the acoustic properties describing the note structure.

Species	Notes per individual		Note duration (ms)		Envelope 20		Envelope 50		Envelope 80		Ascending phase (ms)		Pulse number		Pulse rate	
	mean	sd	mean	sd	mean	sd	mean	sd	mean	sd	mean	sd	mean	sd	mean	sd
<i>B. albilabris</i>	34.000	18.358	498.224	136.243	0.208	0.069	0.072	0.017	0.022	0.010	301.828	146.720	14.489	2.699	28.080	5.497
<i>B. boehmei</i>	25.667	18.978	46.442	15.463	0.414	0.089	0.188	0.046	0.064	0.024	30.086	10.046	9.021	3.517	166.873	35.841
<i>B. burgeri</i>	15.200	6.925	34.446	11.221	0.669	0.133	0.350	0.116	0.146	0.068	17.130	10.165	7.655	3.885	180.477	65.628
<i>B. picturatus</i>	25.400	17.444	43.767	11.478	0.613	0.109	0.343	0.077	0.132	0.041	13.154	6.399	7.223	2.800	139.028	42.693
<i>B. reticulatus A</i>	4.667	2.658	175.814	29.073	0.708	0.069	0.323	0.080	0.096	0.036	111.508	33.274	51.900	5.291	293.492	30.886
<i>B. reticulatus B</i>	2.500	0.707	28.576	7.243	0.639	0.101	0.303	0.067	0.097	0.062	14.966	6.533	6.400	4.930	171.420	107.041
<i>B. aff. sibilans</i>	66.500	62.763	58.831	21.994	0.866	0.095	0.622	0.155	0.232	0.102	21.045	12.391	3.255	2.719	33.503	38.599
<i>G. boulengeri</i>	28.818	13.265	54.721	5.027	0.733	0.076	0.368	0.085	0.162	0.067	5.220	2.761	1.919	1.201	16.523	21.634
<i>G. cornutus</i>	216.250	71.609	109.864	12.829	0.649	0.078	0.241	0.050	0.063	0.027	9.238	5.316	21.675	3.356	188.364	21.882
<i>G. malagasius</i>	14.158	12.898	925.563	282.534	0.138	0.049	0.068	0.014	0.032	0.009	349.855	165.786	33.922	8.107	37.033	7.407
<i>G. sculpturatus</i>	50.825	29.339	79.278	9.324	0.626	0.062	0.348	0.065	0.119	0.047	42.111	12.414	8.159	2.126	89.353	20.427
<i>G. liber</i>	41.889	38.524	49.621	22.401	0.416	0.172	0.190	0.098	0.069	0.037	11.593	11.098	5.447	4.266	73.939	52.050
<i>G. depressiceps</i>	8.474	5.389	186.702	68.907	0.214	0.094	0.189	0.526	0.071	0.230	81.188	41.471	5.293	2.269	22.401	11.860
<i>G. tornieri</i>	27.667	10.263	23.224	4.489	0.575	0.094	0.312	0.098	0.118	0.059	3.692	2.456	5.017	1.535	176.817	72.955
<i>M. albofrenatus</i>	59.400	25.246	66.194	7.834	0.369	0.102	0.201	0.049	0.095	0.028	15.810	5.858	11.827	3.428	163.971	50.078
<i>M. betsileanus</i>	15.857	9.469	2131.094	735.439	0.238	0.055	0.118	0.025	0.040	0.014	500.684	321.744	123.797	36.270	59.187	11.160
<i>M. biporus</i>	20.667	18.903	325.771	128.424	0.158	0.147	0.047	0.031	0.021	0.012	76.678	43.858	10.603	8.291	27.865	11.368
<i>M. melanopleura</i>	61.500	25.648	41.635	6.881	0.690	0.136	0.307	0.105	0.101	0.052	7.723	2.211	9.412	3.471	203.150	85.604
<i>M. opiparis</i>	43.133	22.242	90.752	10.593	0.456	0.081	0.210	0.042	0.080	0.030	12.282	4.722	16.238	2.817	168.004	25.018
<i>S. aglavei A</i>	6.882	3.352	74.620	12.175	0.693	0.139	0.255	0.186	0.085	0.105	5.480	2.006	1.139	0.538	2.256	8.714
<i>S. aglavei B</i>	5.270	3.942	139.962	20.136	0.514	0.089	0.207	0.046	0.058	0.021	53.376	17.939	13.005	2.330	86.661	16.965
<i>S. phantasticus</i>	23.571	10.778	18.053	5.774	0.415	0.166	0.191	0.087	0.101	0.052	5.214	2.270	1.000	0.000	0.000	0.000

Table 17 – Canonical loadings of the three envelope descriptors, explained variance (%) and cumulative proportion (%) of the first two principal components.

	PC1	PC2
Envelope20	0.55	-0.73
Envelope50	0.62	0.04
Envelope80	0.56	0.68
Variance Explained (%)	84.26	13.62
Cumulative Proportion (%)	84.26	97.84

Figure 40 – Boxplot representing the distribution along the first principal component of the PCA performed on envelope descriptors of the sampled species ranked according to their median values. Colours help distinguish species included in different genera.

The first group (*G. malagasius*, *G. depressiceps*, *B. albilabris*, *M. biporus* and *M. betsileanus*) includes species that mit pulsed notes (Figure 41). With the exception of *Spinomantis*, all the recorded genera have a species in this group. The species of this group are those with the longest note durations, ranging from 172.17 ms of *G. depressiceps* to 2309.79 ms of *M. betsileanus* (Table 16)

Figure 41 – Note oscillograms of the species of the pulsed group, ordered for PC1 scores and coloured per genus. A: *Gephyromantis malagasius*. B: *Guibemantis depressiceps*. C: *Boophis albilabris*. D: *Mantidactylus biporus*. E: *Mantidactylus betsileanus*.

The second and third groups identified in the boxplot of Figure 40 comprised species with consistently short note durations (ranging from *S. phantasticus* at 18.04 ms to *B. reticulatus* at 145.88 ms), but with markedly different patterns of amplitude modulation. Figure 42 shows the distribution of peak rate across these species, a parameter that reflects the degree of amplitude modulation within each note. Weakly modulated notes (sometimes nearly tonal, as in *S. phantasticus*) show few peaks (in some cases, only one), whereas highly modulated notes contain numerous peaks.

Species distribution along the peak rate-axis mirrors these differences in modulation, allowing us to identify three groups: a first group on the left side of the x-axis (*S. aglavei* Note Type A, *S. phantasticus*, *G. boulengeri* and *B. aff. sibilans*), characterised by weak modulation (median peak rate < 50 Hz) (e.g., “tonal-like” note); a second group (*G. liber*, *S. aglavei* note type B and *G. sculpturatus*) with moderate modulation (50 Hz < median peak rate < 100 Hz), still perceived in the temporal domain as distinct amplitude fluctuations (e.g., “croak-like” notes); and a third, more heterogeneous group with high modulation (median peak rate > 100 Hz). In this latter group, the rapid modulation is no longer perceived as discrete temporal fluctuations but is instead integrated into a continuous sound, thereby contributing to the note's spectral structure.

Oscillograms of the species included in the tonal group are shown in Figure 43; those of species included in the modulated group are shown in Figure 44 and Figure 45.

In the following, we analyse pulsed and modulated notes separately, with modulated notes further subdivided into tonal and amplitude-modulated types.

Figure 42 - Boxplot representing the distribution along the peak rate parameter of the non-pulsed group ranked according to their median values. Colours help distinguish species included in different genera.

Figure 43 - Note oscillograms of the species of the tonal group, ordered for pulse rate values and coloured per genus. A: *Spinomantis aglavei* (Note type A). B: *Spinomantis phantasticus*. C: *Gephyromantis boulengeri*. D: *Boophis aff. sibilans*.

Figure 44 - Note oscillograms of the species of the modulated group, ordered for peak rate values and coloured per genus. A: *Guibemantis liber*. B: *Spinomantis aglavei* (Note Type B). C: *Gephyromantis sculpturatus*. D: *Boophis picturatus*. E: *Mantidactylus albofrenatus*. F: *Guibemantis tornieri*. G: *Boophis boehmei*. H: *Mantidactylus opiparis*.

Figure 45 - Note oscillograms of the species of the modulated group, ordered for peak rate values and coloured per genus. I: *Boophis burgeri*. J: *Boophis reticulatus* (Note Type B). K: *Gephyromantis cornutus*. L: *Mantidactylus melanopleura*. M: *Boophis reticulatus* (Note Type A).

3.4.2.1 Pulsed notes

We performed a PCA on three acoustic properties of pulsed notes: note duration, pulse number, and ascending phase. Results are shown in Table 18. The first principal component alone explains most of the variance (92.93%) and the three parameters have similar weighting on this component, suggesting that high scores of this component reflect notes of long duration, with a high number of pulses and long ascending phases. High scores of the second principal component, which explains 5.74% of the total variance, mainly describe the contrast occurring in notes with a long ascending phase and a relatively low number of pulses.

Table 18 – Canonical loadings of the three temporal and peak descriptors, explained variance (%) and cumulative proportion (%) of the first two principal components for the pulsed group.

Pulsed group	PC1	PC2
Note Duration	0.59	-0.25
Peak Number	0.58	-0.53
Ascending Phase	0.56	0.81
Variance Explained (%)	92.93	5.74
Cumulative Proportion (%)	92.93	98.67

Figure 46 shows a scatterplot of the five species along the PC1 and PC2 axes. The point distributions for the five species show no overlap, indicating clear interspecific differences in call temporal structure. Although PCA produces orthogonal components on the full dataset, a visual correlation between PC1 and PC2 emerges when considering the single species, suggesting that, within each species, individuals emitting longer notes also have longer ascending phases and a relatively lower number of pulses. Due to its note duration (2.31 ± 0.64 s) and its high pulse number (125.3 ± 22.26), *M. betsileanus* occupies an isolated position in the lower-right of the scatterplot. All individuals of *G. depressiceps* cluster closely on the left side of the plot, confirming the highly stereotyped structure of their vocalisations (Note duration = 0.17 ± 0.04 s). Groups of individuals of *B. albilabris*, *G. malagasius*, and *M. betsileanus*, by contrast, are more widely distributed across the plot, suggesting that temporal parameters such as the ascending phase and note duration are less conserved and that intraspecific variation is higher.

Figure 46 – Scatterplot showing the distribution of the five species included in the pulsed group along the first two principal components of the PCA performed on variables of note duration, number of pulses and ascending phase.

Table 19 shows the results of the general linear models that investigate the effect of temperature and body size (SVL) on the three acoustic properties considered (note duration, peak number and ascending phase), including the species as a random factor.

We found no statistically significant effects of either temperature or SVL on note duration (M1, M2, M3 in Table 19). However, comparison of a random-intercept model with a random-slope model for temperature indicated that the latter provided a slightly significant better fit than the former ($\chi^2 = 7.486$, $df = 2$, $p = 0.02$), suggesting that the effect of temperature varies among species.

Similar results were observed when we investigated the effects of temperature and SVL on peak number. In these models, we included note duration as a covariate. Its effect is not reported in Table 19, but it was always highly significant ($p < 10^{-6}$). Random-intercept models did not show any effects of peak number, but the random-slope model of temperature on peak number showed a highly significant better fit than the random-intercept model ($\chi^2 = 16.664$, $df = 2$, $p < 0.001$) (Table 19).

Unlike note duration and peak number, the ascending phase appears to be unaffected by either SVL or environmental temperature and no significant differences were observed between the random-intercept and the random-slope models with temperature as an independent variable (Table 19).

Table 19 – Coefficients (β), standard errors (SE) and p values of each random-intercept model performed. ANOVA column reports the results of the ANOVA between the random-intercept and the random-slope model for the considered parameter as response variable (environmental temperature or SVL). M1: model including both environmental temperature and SVL. M2: model including only environmental temperature. M3: model including only SVL.

Model	Environmental temperature			SVL			ANOVA		
	β	SE	p	β	SE	p	χ^2	df	p
M1 - Note duration	-0.033	0.040	0.410	-0.007	0.015	0.644			
M2 - Note duration	-0.034	0.040	0.404				7.486	2.000	0.024
M3 - Note duration				-0.007	0.015	0.634	2.703	2.000	0.259
M1 - Peak number	1.153	1.127	0.311	-0.373	0.502	0.488			
M2 - Peak number	1.139	1.127	0.317				16.664	2.000	<0.001
M3 - Peak number				-0.361	0.504	0.502	4.381	2.000	0.112
M1 - Ascending phase	0.008	0.009	0.363	0.002	0.001	0.129			
M2 - Ascending phase	0.006	0.009	0.488				0.801	2.000	0.670
M3 - Ascending phase				0.002	0.001	0.158	1.949	2.000	0.377

3.4.2.2 Modulated notes

PCA performed on the temporal variables of note duration, peak number and ascending phase of the modulated group are reported in Table 20. The first principal component accounts for 67.11% of the total variance and it is positively correlated with all three acoustic variables. PC2 explains 23.84% of the remaining variance and it is positively correlated with the ascending phase and negatively correlated with the peak number. High values of these components indicate notes with a relatively long ascending phase and a relatively low peak number.

Table 20 – Canonical loadings of the three temporal and peak descriptors, explained variance (%) and cumulative proportion (%) of the first two principal components for the modulated group.

Modulated group	PC1	PC2
Note Duration	0.65	-0.05
Peak Number	0.56	-0.65
Ascending Phase	0.52	0.76
Variance Explained (%)	67.11	23.84
Cumulative Proportion (%)	67.11	90.95

Figure 47 shows the distribution of recorded individuals along the PC1 and PC2 axes. As observed for pulsed notes, overlap among species is minimal, indicating that they occupy distinct regions of the acoustic space. The scatterplot shows that species with negative PC1 scores (short notes with few peaks) have PC2 scores close to 0. In contrast, those with positive PC1 scores tend to split into two groups: the first group shows a positive correlation between the two PCs, whereas the second shows a negative correlation. The first group includes *G. cornutus* and *M. opiparis*, which produce notes with short ascending phase and a relatively high number of peaks ($PC2 < 0$); contrarily, the second group, including *B. boehmei*, *S. aglavei* (Note type B) and *G. sculpturatus*, emit notes with proportionally longer ascending phase and with a relatively smaller number of peaks ($PC2 > 0$). In this plot, *B. reticulatus* represents an exceptional case, because its notes have an exceptionally high number of peaks (42.31 ± 17.36) relative to its duration ($145.88 \text{ ms} \pm 60 \text{ ms}$) (see also the oscillogram in Figure 45).

Figure 47 - Scatterplot showing the distribution of the species included in the modulated group along the first two principal components of the PCA performed on variables of note duration, number of pulses and ascending phase.

Table 21 shows the results of the general linear models with the three acoustic parameters as dependent factors, species as a random factor and temperature and SVL as covariates. These analyses include the species with at least 9 recorded individuals.

The first series of models had note duration as the dependent variable. The model (M1) that includes both temperature and SVL as independent factors shows a significant positive effect of SVL and only a weak negative effect of temperature. The effect of temperature increases when SVL is not included as a predictor (M2), but it remains weak. Likewise, excluding temperature from the model (M3) strengthens the effect of SVL. Finally, the comparison between the random-intercept and random-slope model of SVL on note duration shows no significant differences in fit (ANOVA: $\chi^2 = 2.216$, $df = 2$, $p = 0.330$). Overall, these results suggest that in species with modulated notes, larger individuals tend to emit longer notes, and that the constraining effect of body size is similar across species.

The second and third series of models considered, respectively, pulse number and ascending phase as the dependent variables. In both model series, neither temperature nor SVL had a significant effect on call properties. In addition to temperature and SVL, these models included note duration as a covariate, whose effects were consistently positive and

highly significant ($p < 0.001$; not shown in Table 21). ANOVA comparing the random intercept and random slope models investigating the relationship between note duration and ascending phase reveals that the random slope model fits better ($\chi^2 = 13.67$, $df = 2$, $p = 0.001$), suggesting this relationship varies across the considered species.

Table 21 – Coefficients (β), standard errors (SE) and p values (p) of each random-intercept model performed. ANOVA column reports the results of the ANOVA between the random-intercept and the random-slope model for the considered parameter as the response variable (environmental temperature or SVL). M1: model including both environmental temperature and SVL. M2: model including only environmental temperature. M3: model including only SVL.

Model	Environmental temperature			SVL			ANOVA		
	β	SE	p	β	SE	p	χ^2	df	p
M1 - Note duration	-1.470	0.891	0.101	1.350	0.563	0.019			
M2 - Note duration	-1.746	0.887	0.051				1.993	2.000	0.369
M3 - Note duration				1.476	0.558	0.010	2.216	2.000	0.330
M1 - Peak number	0.180	0.156	0.249	0.060	0.098	0.538			
M2 - Peak number	0.172	0.155	0.271				0.925	2.000	0.630
M3 - Peak number				0.049	0.097	0.616	4.466	2.000	0.107
M1 - Ascending phase	0.419	0.733	0.587	-0.139	0.300	0.645			
M2 - Ascending phase	0.579	0.466	0.215				3.547	2.000	0.170
M3 - Ascending phase				-0.119	0.303	0.696	0.010	2.000	0.995

For the modulated group, we also selected the four most sampled species (*B. boehmei*, *G. cornutus*, *G. sculpturatus* and *S. aglavei*) to assess the relationship between the considered note descriptors (note duration, number of peaks and ascending phase) (Table 22).

Independent of note duration, which always has a significant positive effect, in some species the ascending phase significantly affects pulse number, whereas in others it does not. The comparison between *G. cornutus* and *G. sculpturatus*, species of the subgenus *Duboisimantis*, is of particular interest because in *G. sculpturatus* notes have longer ascending phases, which negatively impact pulse number ($\beta = -64.274$, $SE = 21.036$, $p = 0.004$), whereas in *G. cornutus* the effect is opposite ($\beta = 232.541$, $SE = 100.333$, $p = 0.026$). Our results suggest that in species whose notes reach the amplitude peak at the end of the note, with ascending phases proportionally longer (such as *G. sculpturatus*), peak rate tends to increase during the ascending phase because the peak distance decreases, so peak rate increases with intensity. This acceleration occurs throughout the note, so the

peak rate is lower, and notes with longer ascending phases lead to a lower number of peaks, with a negative correlation between ascending phase and peak number. In *G. cornutus*, by contrast, the ascending phase positively influences the number of peaks, with longer ascending phases resulting in more peaks. The third observed pattern is a positive but not significant influence of the ascending phase on the number of peaks (*B. boehmei*: $\beta = 9.296$, $SE = 55.402$, $p = 0.868$; *S. aglavei*: $\beta = 19.047$, $SE = 36.001$, $p = 0.600$), suggesting that in species where the amplitude peak is not at the beginning or at the end of the note, but is reached in the middle of it, the ascending phase has a lower influence on the peak number.

Table 22 – Coefficients (β), standard errors (SE) and p-values (p) of the random-intercept models performed on each species to assess the influence of the ascending phase on the number of pulses.

	β	SE	p
<i>B. boehmei</i>	9.296	55.402	0.868
<i>G. cornutus</i>	232.541	100.333	0.026
<i>G. sculpturatus</i>	-64.274	21.036	0.004
<i>S. aglavei</i>	19.047	36.001	0.600

3.4.2.3 Tonal notes

For the tonal group, no PCA was performed because the peak number parameter was removed. These species indeed emit notes with a single or few peaks, so we only considered note duration and ascending phase. The scatterplot of these species' distribution along the two parameters is shown below in Figure 48. Notes of *B. aff. sibilans* distribution in the scatterplot reflects their high variability; as previously mentioned, it could potentially be due to the grouping of more than one species part of the same complex or due to extreme intraspecific variability. Other species in this group are more densely distributed, especially *S. phantasticus*, whose notes maintain a highly conserved structure, preserved also at higher levels of organisation as call series, as further described in the bouts section. The two species of *Spinomantis*, as well as *G. boulengeri*, have a low inter-individual variability in terms of ascending phase (always shorter than 5.5 ms), whereas notes of *B. aff. sibilans* have ascending phases ranging from 10 ms to 30 ms. Within this

group, the shortest notes are emitted by *S. phantasticus* (mean = 18.05 ms, SD = 5.77 ms), followed by *G. boulengeri* (mean = 54.72 ms, SD = 5.03 ms).

Figure 48 - Scatterplot showing the distribution of the species included in the tonal group along note duration and ascending phase.

Table 23 shows the results of the GLM analyses with note duration and ascending phase as dependent factors and SVL and temperature as independent factors. Neither temperature (models M1 and M2) nor SVL (models M1 and M3) showed a significant overall effect on note duration. However, comparison between the random-intercept and random-slope models for SVL revealed a significant improvement in model fit for the latter (ANOVA: $\chi^2 = 7.019$, $df = 2$, $p = 0.030$). This indicates that, although SVL does not exert a consistent effect across species, its influence on note duration varies among species. Specifically, note duration was positively affected by SVL in *B. aff. sibilans* ($\beta = 6.519$, $SE = 4.762$, $p = 0.229$) and in *S. aglavei* ($\beta = 1.631$, $SE = 1.399$, $p = 0.269$), but negatively affected in *S. phantasticus* ($\beta = -0.663$, $SE = 0.824$, $p = 0.435$) and in *G. boulengeri* ($\beta = -0.858$, $SE = 1.794$, $p = 0.645$). However, none of these models yielded statistically significant results (always $p > 0.05$).

The GLMs with the ascending phase as the dependent variable show similar results. Neither SVL nor environmental temperature shows a consistent effect on this acoustic parameter. However, the random-slope model for SVL fits significantly better than the random-intercept model ($\chi^2 = 13.518$, $df = 2$, $p = 0.001$), suggesting that the SVL effect differs among species. In these models, note duration was always included as a covariate. Its effect (not shown in Table 23) was always positive and statistically significant ($\beta = 0.795$, $SE = 0.108$, $p < 0.001$). These effects vary among species since the random-slope model fits better than the random-intercept model ($\chi^2 = 36.803$, $df = 2$, $p < 0.001$).

Table 23 – Coefficients (β), standard errors (SE) and p values (p) of each random-intercept model performed. ANOVA column reports the results of the ANOVA between the random-intercept and the random-slope model for the considered parameter as the response variable (environmental temperature or SVL). M1: model including both environmental temperature and SVL. M2: model including only environmental temperature. M3: model including only SVL.

Model	Environmental temperature			SVL			ANOVA		
	β	SE	p	β	SE	p	χ^2	df	p
M1 - Note duration	-2.585	1.605	0.117	1.457	0.950	0.139			
M2 - Note duration	-2.516	1.657	0.138				1.064	2.000	0.588
M3 - Note duration				1.393	0.961	0.162	7.019	2.000	0.030
M1 - Ascending phase	1.130	1.157	0.336	0.369	0.680	0.594			
M2 - Ascending phase	1.155	1.149	0.322				0.088	2.000	0.957
M3 - Ascending phase				0.408	0.671	0.550	13.518	2.000	0.001

3.4.3 Bout analyses

An example of two distinct types of note organisation is provided by the comparison between *Spinomantis phantasticus* and *Gephyromantis cornutus*.

Figure 49 shows the oscillogram of a typical bout of calls of *S. phantasticus*. Males of this species emit double-click “metallic” calls, and we identified each click as a note, each couple as a call and the whole temporally defined group as a bout of calls. This species, as shown in the oscillogram, can also emit single notes at the beginning or at the end of a call series, but every bout has at least a well-defined couple of clicks.

In contrast, Figure 50 displays the oscillogram of a bout of calls from *G. cornutus*. In this species, notes correspond to calls and are emitted irregularly, without a precise, stereotyped and maintained structure. Bouts are therefore highly variable in notes per bout and in bout duration, since no real organisation in call series seem to occur in this species’ vocalisations.

Figure 49 – Oscillogram of two bouts of calls emitted by a male of *Spinomantis phantasticus*. The legend on the bottom left helps the interpretation of each level of organisation. As reported, the time is an artefact for aesthetic purposes; real inter-bout values for this species are typically higher than 30 s.

Figure 50 - Oscillogram of three bouts of notes emitted by a male of *Gephyromantis cornutus*. The legend at the bottom left helps interpret each level of organisation.

Results of the bout analyses are shown in Table 24 below. We identified five groups of species in our dataset and classified them based on the level of stereotypy in their note organisations. The first group (group 0) includes three species (*B. boehmei*, *B. picturatus*, and *S. aglavei* Note Type B) whose notes are typically emitted solely, not organised in bouts. In the *Boophis* spp. notes can be grouped in bout, but it represents a less-used type of vocalisation in their vocal repertoires (single-note bouts: *B. boehmei* = 93.70%; *B. picturatus* = 91.48%). In *S. aglavei*, on the contrary, the “croak” note is never emitted in series (single note bouts: 100%). The second group (group 1) includes four species (*B. albilabris*, *G. cornutus*, *G. malagasius* and *M. betsileanus*) in which the high bout duration values and their standard deviations reflect notes emitted in series but not showing a conserved organisation into bouts (*B. albilabris*: Mean bout duration = 73.75 s, SD = 42.06 s; *G. cornutus*: Mean bout duration = 129.52 s, SD = 63.69 s; *G. malagasius*: Mean bout duration = 32.15 s, SD = 23.37 s; *M. betsileanus*: Mean bout duration = 180.98 s, SD = 82.42 s). These species (except for *G. cornutus*, the remaining three are included in the pulsed group) emit notes regularly and for long periods, but their vocalisations seem not to be organised into higher-order temporal structures, with notes

emitted at relatively conserved intervals in *B. albilabris* and *G. cornutus* (*B. albilabris*: Mean note period = 2421.17 ms, SD = 533.16 ms; *G. cornutus*: Mean note period = 908.97 ms, SD = 398.49 ms). The third group (group 2) includes species whose notes can be organised in bouts (*B. burgeri*, *B. reticulatus*, *G. liber* and *M. biporus*), but this organisation is highly variable and single notes are rather frequently emitted, since the percentage of single note bouts in this species ranges between 20 and 80%. The fourth group (*B. aff. sibilans*, *G. sculpturatus*, *G. depressiceps*, *M. opiparis* and *S. aglavei* Note Type A) includes species in which the organisation in bout is exhibited more frequently and this temporal structure is highly conserved in their vocalisations. However, contrary to the fifth group, in this group single note bouts can be emitted more frequently (percentages ranging from 9.90 to 18.73%). As mentioned, the fifth group (*G. boulengeri*, *G. tornieri*, *M. albofrenatus*, *M. melanopleura* and *S. phantasticus*) includes species whose notes are emitted in series following an extremely stereotyped structure, which we defined as call. Some species in this group never exhibited single-note bouts (*G. tornieri*, *M. albofrenatus*, and *S. phantasticus*), suggesting that this higher level of organisation contains species-specific information that helps the female recognise males during the breeding season. As previously mentioned, *S. phantasticus* emits double-click notes in series, and for this species, due to the highly stereotyped distance between the two clicks (mean note period = 0.08 s, SD = 0.01 s), this pair of notes should represent the call. However, results in Table 24 resume the bout descriptors values considering the threshold obtained by imposing the maximum detectable threshold at 30 times the note duration, and in the case of *S. phantasticus* this methodical choice highlights the higher “bout of calls” level, the group of double clicks, which is less maintained both in terms of bout duration (Mean = 1.37 s, SD = 0.42 s) and number of notes (Mean = 9.69, SD = 2.81). Using 15 times the note duration as the maximum detectable threshold, we obtained call descriptors for this species, which was the only one relevantly differing depending on the used approach. This different approach also allowed us to highlight the presence, despite being rare (4.43%), of single clicks, always followed (or preceded) by at least a couple of clicks, since no single bout is detected using the “30” approach. Call parameters of *S. phantasticus* are reported as *S. phantasticus** in Table 24.

Table 24 – Bout parameters (percentage of single-note bouts, bout duration, number of notes, note-period, inter-bout and note duration) means and standard deviations (SD) of each species. Species are grouped based on their single-note percentage and bout duration (which allowed to separate group 1). Number of considered individuals per species is reported in column “N”.

Species	Group	N	Single-note bout	Bout duration (s)		Number of notes		Note-period (ms)		Inter-bout (s)		Note duration (ms)	
			(%)	mean	SD	mean	SD	mean	SD	mean	SD	mean	SD
<i>B.boehmei</i>	0	21	93.70	0.74	0.37	5.04	2.91	157.38	40.43	2.31	3.13	47.62	7.89
<i>B. picturatus</i>	0	2	91.48	1.56	0.71	2.53	0.98	747.32	132.67	42.76	63.21	45.72	7.04
<i>S. aglavei B</i>	0	31	100.00					0.00	0.00			139.28	19.49
<i>B. albilabris</i>	1	5	0.00	73.75	42.06	32.70	20.34	2421.17	533.16	33.94		466.07	145.76
<i>G. cornutus</i>	1	40	3.69	129.52	63.69	175.36	97.07	908.97	398.49	6.76	4.96	108.61	13.43
<i>G. malagasius</i>	1	14	57.58	32.15	23.37	10.04	8.57	4486.92	3864.96	58.26	21.37	828.34	210.86
<i>M. betsileanus</i>	1	14	7.14	180.98	82.42	15.39	9.95	15039.81	7314.02	81.88	26.03	2309.79	642.54
<i>B. burgeri</i>	2	10	62.71	0.62	0.23	6.07	2.42	104.42	12.40	2.42	1.03	36.97	7.51
<i>B. reticulatus</i>	2	4	39.72	1.00	1.61	2.27	0.43	1060.00	980.61	92.56	76.84	181.38	22.30
<i>G. liber</i>	2	8	46.65	2.25	1.63	5.95	3.96	396.60	268.34	26.46	23.29	70.49	19.21
<i>M. biporus</i>	2	2	74.24	1.90	1.20	2.60	0.85	406.78	104.05	7.89	1.50	49.46	10.35
<i>B. aff. sibilans</i>	3	6	9.90	3.17	1.47	9.31	3.32	3205.09	738.21	20.88	13.63	172.17	42.09
<i>G. depressiceps</i>	3	19	17.03	9.31	3.87	3.18	0.83	814.42	34.53	127.51	80.85	341.79	61.65
<i>M. opiparis</i>	3	14	18.73	8.74	2.27	23.36	5.48	448.54	226.82	320.97	257.03	91.05	6.61
<i>G. sculpturatus</i>	3	40	13.69	2.35	1.57	6.43	3.20	368.62	44.37	42.98	31.43	82.59	9.33
<i>S. aglavei A</i>	3	15	14.71	1.94	0.55	6.43	1.80	301.39	22.98	25.75	23.65	73.83	7.59
<i>G. boulengeri</i>	4	11	3.03	2.36	0.72	11.73	3.11	197.33	21.55	239.21	114.99	53.78	3.64
<i>G. tornieri</i>	4	3	0.00	0.31	0.05	3.18	0.06	94.98	14.41	43.28	13.62	23.45	1.68
<i>M. albofrenatus</i>	4	10	0.00	4.38	1.88	24.81	10.53	184.75	34.97	194.36	122.50	64.95	4.35
<i>M. melanopleura</i>	4	10	2.00	2.97	0.53	24.95	3.74	118.31	6.97	218.08	76.85	42.38	3.78
<i>S. phantasticus</i>	4	21	0.00	1.37	0.42	9.69	2.81	139.28	12.00	243.06	150.49	18.04	3.87
<i>S. phantasticus*</i>	4	21	4.43	0.15	0.02	2.00	0.00	83.36	8.96	30.85	39.62	18.04	3.87

The species distribution along single bout percentage and bout duration (s) is shown in Figure 51. Species of group 1 have not been represented in the plot. This plot visually separates group 0 (single-note bout percentages above 91.48%) and group 2 (single-note bout percentages ranging from 39.72 to 74.24%). Group 3 distribution is wider due to the higher bout duration of *G. depressiceps* (Mean = 9.31 s) and *M. opiparis* (Mean = 8.74 s), whereas the “call group” (group 4) is aligned along approximately 0% single bout percentage.

Figure 51 – Species distribution along single bout percentage and mean bout duration. Group 1 has not been included in the plot.

3.4.4 Spectral analyses

Values of SVL and dominant frequency were log-transformed to linearise their allometric relationship before performing statistical analyses. Species were used as a random effect in the following models. We detected a significant negative correlation between animal size and dominant frequency across the whole dataset ($\beta = -0.279$, $SE = 0.095$, $p = 0.004$) (Figure 52). This correlation is better explained by a random intercept model, as demonstrated by the not-significant ANOVA contrasting it with the random slope model ($\chi^2 = 4.180$, $df = 2$, $p = 0.124$). By introducing the note type (pulsed, modulated or tonal) as

a fixed factor in the model, the significance of the individual size increase ($p < 0.001$) and the model fits better (ANOVA: $\chi^2 = 6.731$, $df = 2$, $p = 0.035$). Independently of the individual size, species emitting pulsed notes are characterised by a dominant frequency significantly lower than both those emitting modulated notes ($\beta = -0.353$, $SE = 0.153$, $p = 0.036$) and those emitting tonal notes ($\beta = -0.424$, $SE = 0.192$, $p = 0.044$).

The scatterplot of Figure 52 highlights several species whose dominant frequencies deviate markedly from those expected by their size. In particular, the two species of the subgenus *Brygomantis* (*Mantidactylus betsileanus* and *Mantidactylus biporus*) emit pulsed notes with unusually low dominant frequency, whereas *Gephyromantis sculpturatus* calls at substantially higher frequencies than other congeneric species of similar size (e.g. *Gephyromantis cornutus*). In this latter case, the difference arises because the dominant frequency of *G. sculpturatus* corresponds to the second harmonic, whereas in all other species it corresponds to the fundamental frequency. By contrast, in *Mantidactylus*, we found no evidence that energy peaks occur at different harmonics; thus, the observed deviation likely reflects an ability of these species to sensibly lower their fundamental frequency.

Figure 52 – Species distribution along the log-transformed SVL and the log-transformed dominant frequency.

3.4.5 Phylogenetical analyses

Phylogenetic signal in the note amplitude modulation (using the PC1 resulting from the PCA performed on Envelope20, Envelope50 and Envelope 80), assessed with Blomberg's K and Pagel's λ tests, was absent independently of the performed test (Blomberg's $K = 0.647$, $p = 0.430$; Pagel's $\lambda < 0.001$, $p = 1$).

Results of the phylogenetically-corrected Pearson's correlation test between envelope PC1 (i.e., the level of amplitude modulation) and calling-site height are shown in the boxplot of Figure 53. The analysis was performed on all sampled species, grouped by calling height (cm).

The correlation coefficient indicates a strong positive correlation between envelope PC1 and calling height ($r = 0.695$, $p = 0.001$). Independently of phylogeny, amplitude modulation is more pronounced in species calling from lower spots in the vegetation, compared to those vocalising from higher positions. This pattern is particular evident in ground-calling species, which emit highly modulated, pulsed notes.

Figure 53 – Boxplot showing the relationship between call height (cm) and the first envelope principal component. Species have been grouped per call height.

Adjusted means and standard errors of the log-transformed dominant frequencies obtained for further phylogenetic analyses are summarised in Table 25.

Table 25 – Adjusted means and standard errors (SE) of the log-transformed dominant frequencies for each species.

Species	Dominant frequency	SE
<i>Boophis albilabris</i>	6.97	0.15
<i>Boophis boehmei</i>	7.82	0.03
<i>Boophis burgeri</i>	7.54	0.03
<i>Boophis picturatus</i>	8.22	0.05
<i>Boophis reticulatus</i>	7.78	0.04
<i>Boophis aff. sibilans</i>	8.15	0.04
<i>Gephyromantis boulengeri</i>	8.22	0.06
<i>Gephyromantis cornutus</i>	7.44	0.02
<i>Gephyromantis malagasius</i>	8.17	0.08
<i>Gephyromantis sculpturatus</i>	8.14	0.03
<i>Guibemantis depressiceps</i>	7.67	0.03
<i>Guibemantis liber</i>	7.97	0.05
<i>Mantidactylus albofrenatus</i>	8.20	0.08
<i>Mantidactylus betsileanus</i>	7.33	0.04
<i>Mantidactylus biporus</i>	7.24	0.09
<i>Mantidactylus melanopleura</i>	7.99	0.03
<i>Mantidactylus opiparis</i>	8.02	0.05
<i>Spinomantis aglavei</i> Note type A	7.60	0.05
<i>Spinomantis aglavei</i> Note type B	7.58	0.04
<i>Spinomantis phantasticus</i>	7.70	0.03

Phylogenetic signal of the dominant frequency was low and not statistically significant ($K = 0.734$, $p = 0.154$; $\lambda = <0.001$, $p = 1$). Overall, the Pearson's correlation test corrected for phylogeny showed a positive, but not significant, correlation between dominant frequency and calling site height ($r = 0.392$, $p = 0.108$) (Figure 54). Species calling from the ground showed the lowest dominant frequencies, whereas no consistent pattern emerged among species calling at higher elevations. Indeed, species calling at “50-100 cm” above the ground (*G. liber*, *M. albofrenatus*, *M. melanopleura* and *M. opiparis*) emitted notes with dominant frequencies ranging from 2958.153 Hz in *M. melanopleura* to 4138.678 Hz in *M. albofrenatus*. although higher than those expected for species of such small body size (19-23 mm in *M. albofrenatus*, up to 40 mm in *M. melanopleura*).

Figure 54 - Boxplot showing the relationship between call height (cm) and the log-transformed dominant frequency. Species have been grouped per call height.

4 Discussion

By integrating morphological and bioacoustic results, we identified patterns of variation within the family Mantellidae and added phylogenetic and ecological interpretations to investigate the causes of this diversification.

4.1 Morphology

Our morphometric results indicate that most morphological traits exhibit a strong phylogenetic signal, whereas size and eye-to-head ratio do not. Our classic approach was largely influenced by size variation, as PC1 captured 95.1% of the variance, whereas the geometric approach allowed us to consider head and limb shape variation independently of individual size. According to Klingenberg (2016), the classic and geometric morphometric approaches differ in the specific aspects of evolution and development investigated, but are logically compatible and unlikely to yield contradictory results. Our results support this statement, as the two approaches yielded similar outcomes in both phylogenetic signal and the major differences detected.

Head's geometric morphometry results are of particular interest, especially along PC1, which accounts for 63.8% of the total variance. This principal component contrasts two distinct head-elongation patterns: along the sagittal plane versus the frontal plane. PC1 head scores separate the two most arboreal genera, *Boophis* and *Spinomantis* ($PC1 > 0$), from the more terrestrial genera ($PC1 < 0$). The similarity in head shape between *Boophis* and *Spinomantis* may reflect either convergent evolution and adaptation to arboreal habits or the conservation of an ancestral trait shared by most species of Boophinae and by early-diverging lineages of Mantellinae (e.g., *Spinomantis* spp., *Guibemantis* spp.). In contrast, other Mantellinae genera (e.g., *Gephyromantis* spp., *Mantidactylus* spp.) share a different head shape, elongated along the sagittal plane, potentially representing an adaptation to more terrestrial or semi-aquatic life.

However, head shape variation along PC1 exhibits a significant phylogenetic signal. The impact of phylogeny in head shape variation was also reported by Bardua et al. (2020), who suggest that interpreting the skull as a single integrated unit may represent an oversimplification because each cranial region may follow distinct evolutionary trajectories.

An additional aspect not considered in this study is life history. In particular, the presence of a feeding larval stage has been hypothesised to influence the evolutionary integration of the anuran skull, although this hypothesis was not supported (Bardua et al., 2021). Other ecological variables not included in this thesis are prey traits (size and mobility), which have been shown to be associated with head shape in some generalist anurans by (Diaz-Perez et al. (2025).

Eye distance and position (PC2 head) have been associated with activity patterns in anurans (Huang et al., 2019). In particular, strictly nocturnal species tend to exhibit a greater interorbital distance than both nocturnal and diurnal species. Additionally, foraging mobility and defensive strategies appear to influence this trait, with species exhibiting slower foraging mobility showing larger interorbital distances. Further studies on the species of Maromizaha could also integrate activity patterns with the observed variation in eye position.

Eye size variation, captured in our study by PC3 head, is generally expected to scale allometrically with body size, with larger animals having relatively smaller eyes. However, contrary to this general trend, our results did not reveal a significant negative correlation between the eye/head ratio and classic PC1, which reflects individual size. Consistent with the findings of Huang et al. (2019) on 44 anuran species in China, we also found no association between habitat and eye size. In contrast, Thomas et al. (2020) reported a significant relationship between eye size and habitat, with fossorial, subfossorial and aquatic species showing a marked reduction in eye size. Although these ecological categories are not fully represented in our dataset, the genus *Mantidactylus* includes several aquatic species, and some of the sampled taxa (e.g., subgenus *Brygoomantis*) are associated with semi-aquatic environments. Nevertheless, no significant differences in eye size (PC3 head) were detected between stream-edge species (the most aquatic-associated habitat in our dataset) and other ecological categories.

Within Mantellidae, larval head shape has been relatively well described for several species (Jovanovic et al., 2009; Vejarano et al., 2006), whereas adult head shape remains less studied. Limited information is available on eye position and size in Mantellidae, but the importance of eye colouration and patterns (iris, sclera, outer iris) has been demonstrated, with these traits having evolved and reversed multiple times within this family and ultimately involved in visual communication. Brightly coloured iris and iris periphery are mainly observed in *Boophis* treefrogs, whereas a frenal streak and dark tympana are found in more terrestrial genera, like *Mantidactylus* or *Gephyromantis* (Amat

et al., 2013). Eye colouration may also contribute to reproductive isolation, as suggested by Glaw & Vences (1997).

Ecological constraints are recognised as drivers of morphological variation. For instance, Moen et al. (2013) demonstrated a strong relationship between ecology and morphology, showing that frogs that use the same microhabitat have evolved similar morphologies. Our results partially support the form-function hypothesis, whereby “morphology changes predictably to meet the functional demands of species along niche gradients” (Basham et al, 2024).

In particular, we detected effects of habitat on limb morphology: stream-edge species exhibited limb proportions that differ significantly from those of forestal and arboreal species, independently of phylogeny. Similar patterns have been observed in other species. Moen et al. (2019), analysing 191 frog species across different ecomorphs, found differences in leg musculature and higher swimming performance in swimming ecomorphs compared to non-swimming ones. Likewise, Basham et al. (2024) found that larger toes relative to their length allow frogs in the tropical rainforests of Gabon to reach greater canopy heights.

Despite these ecological patterns, limb geometric morphometric results (independent of size effects) are highly conserved within genera and a strong phylogenetic signal is evident in limb shape variation. However, these results do not necessarily preclude the role of ecological constraints driving limb variation; indeed, limbs PC1 scores clearly separate arboreal species ($PC1 > 0$) from less or non-arboreal ones ($PC1$ scores < 0), suggesting a joint influence of ecological adaptation and phylogenetic history on limb morphology.

The rearrangement described by PC2 limbs (reflecting variation between anterior and posterior limbs) allows discrimination between different locomotory modes within the sampled species, separating species performing “escape jumps” - single, long-distance jumps (e.g., *G. sculpturatus*) – from those performing “successive hopping”, a locomotory mode typical of more terrestrial species characterised by multiple rapid jumps (e.g., *M. biporus*). Limb proportions are known to vary according to the adopted locomotory mode. Species specialised for long-distance jumping generally have relatively longer hindlimbs, whereas species performing successive hopping exhibit shorter ones (Zug, 1978), and this distinction is also present in the species of our dataset. This relationship is supported in the literature, as jumping performance is positively correlated with hindlimb

length in both juvenile and adult anurans (Zamora-Camacho & Aragón, 2019; Johansson et al., 2010), likely reflecting increased muscular mass (James et al., 2005)

Furthermore, the correlation between PC2 (limbs) and PC2 and PC3 (head), suggests a potential association between locomotory mode and eye size and position. In parallel, the significant correlation between PC1 limbs and PC1 head, with both components separating arboreal and non-arboreal species, reinforces the idea that arboreal taxa have evolved similar head and limb morphologies.

Overall, our findings reveal a strong phylogenetic signal in most observed patterns of morphological variation, except for size. Further research is needed to determine whether the arboreal condition is the primary driver of the convergent shape variation observed in treefrogs. Additionally, the relationship between eye morphology and limb proportions (especially hindlimb length) needs to be further investigated.

4.2 Bioacoustics

Köhler et al. (2017) reviewed call parameters and found that call and note duration, peak rate within notes, number of peaks and dominant frequency are among the most stable acoustic traits, making them particularly informative for taxonomic purposes. Inter-specific variation in both spectral and temporal properties of anuran advertisement calls facilitates species recognition and reduces the risk of hybridisation among closely related species, thus acting as an important premating isolating mechanism (Duellman and Pyles, 1983). Consistent with this framework, these traits appear to be highly conserved across the analysed species, but show remarkable differences among taxa, even among morphologically similar ones. Such variation likely enhances conspecific recognition by females.

Based on the degree of amplitude modulation, we identified three note types: pulsed, modulated and tonal. Overall, amplitude modulation appears to be negatively correlated with calling site height. Indeed, phylogenetic analyses (Blomberg's K and Pagel's λ) indicate that amplitude modulation (captured by PC1 Envelope) does not exhibit a significant phylogenetic signal, and phylogenetically controlled correlation tests reveal a positive association between modulation patterns and calling-site height.

The pulsed-note group includes representatives from most of the genera considered (e.g., *Boophis albilabris*, *Gephyromantis malagasius*, *Guibemantis depressiceps*, *Mantidactylus*

betsileanus, and *Mantidactylus biporus*). With the exception of *G. depressiceps*, these species call from the ground or low vegetation. Their notes are also longer than those of the other two groups. The modulated-note group is more heterogeneous and includes species calling from low (50-100 cm) to high (>150 cm) elevations. The tonal-note group includes a smaller number of species, typically vocalising from higher positions in the canopy (e.g., *Boophis aff. sibilans*, *Spinomantis aglavei* and *Spinomantis phantasticus*). In addition to differences in amplitude modulation, these groups also differ in (size-adjusted) dominant frequencies. In particular, pulsed calls show lower dominant frequencies than modulated or tonal calls, even after accounting for body size. Since this pattern is observed across phylogenetically distant species, it suggests that pulsed notes may have evolved multiple times in response to specific microhabitat conditions.

Our results are consistent with the acoustic adaptation hypothesis (AAH), which posits that environmental selection shapes acoustic signals by favouring traits that enhance propagation and reduce distortion (Morton 1975; Wilkins et al., 2013). Since different environments (or distinct habitats within the same environment) may favour different temporal and spectral properties, the AAH predicts that inter-specific variation in call properties reflects variation in selective pressures acting on the acoustic signal (Everest & Pohlmann, 2009).

Overall, empirical support for the AAH remains mixed, possibly due to the inconsistent use of broad habitat categories and the confounding effects of other evolutionary processes, such as sexual selection. Bosch & de la Riva (2004) found no significant relationship between habitat type and dominant frequency in Bolivian frog species. Goutte et al. (2018) found support for the AAH in torrent frogs, but only for spectral features, which vary with environmental noise. In contrast, no clear effects of calling habitat were detected on call temporal properties. In accordance with AAH prediction, Odendaal et al. (1986) highlighted a lower repetition rate in closed than in open habitats (*Crinia signifera* vs *Crinia riparia*), whereas in central Amazon frogs the dominant frequency was found to be lower in calls of species living in closed habitats than in those living in more open habitats (Zimmermann, 1983).

Tonal notes have been proposed as an evolutionary novelty in two sister species of *Physalaemus* (Leptodactylidae), whose vocal repertoires also include pulsed, noisy warbling notes. Males of *P. lateristriga* produce pulsed or tonal calls, whereas males of *P. olfersii* can switch between these two structures within a call (De Carvalho et al., 2018). We observed a similar pattern in the *Boophis albipunctatus* group, in which both pulsed

and longer tonal whistling notes were recorded. This intra- and interspecific variation in amplitude modulation may represent a mechanism of reproductive isolation within complexes of morphologically similar species.

We also observed an additional pattern that warrants further investigation. Among the modulated-note group, oscillograms often reveal two distinct note “silhouettes” that vary in the timing of peak amplitude. The two species of the subgenus *Duboimantis* provide a clear example of this pattern. *Gephyromantis cornutus* emits notes with a short ascending phase followed by a long descending phase, with the amplitude peak occurring early in the note and the peak rate tending to decrease over time (Figure 55A). In contrast, *Gephyromantis sculpturatus* emits notes with a prolonged ascending phase and a shorter descending phase, in which the peak rate increases progressively until the amplitude peak is reached (Figure 55B).

Figure 55 – Comparison between the oscillogram silhouettes of two species of the subgenus *Duboimantis*. A: Oscillogram of a call of *G. sculpturatus*; B: Oscillogram of a call of *G. cornutus*.

Consistent with these qualitative observations, we detected opposite relationships between ascending phase duration and peak number in the two species: a positive correlation in *G. cornutus* and a negative correlation in *G. sculpturatus*.

The nonlinear oscillator hypothesis (del Olmo et al., 2024) may help understand this pattern of variation. Indeed, differences in the timing of amplitude peaks and in the energy distribution may depend on the vocal mechanism and on the properties (e.g. elasticity) of the vibrating tissues. Vocal sacs (single subgular in *G. cornutus* and paired subgular in *G. sculpturatus*) may also play a role in determining these differences. Although this interpretation remains speculative, it suggests that intra-note amplitude patterns may be

functionally relevant to communication and may provide insight into the biomechanical processes that generate acoustic signals in Mantellidae.

We also assessed the effect of temperature and body size (SVL) on both inter- and intra-specific variation in call properties. As reviewed by Gerhardt & Huber (2002), temporal call properties are mainly affected by temperature, whereas spectral properties by body size. At higher temperatures, muscle contraction-relaxation cycles become shorter, leading to increased pulse rates and reduced note durations. Interestingly, Gerhardt (1978) discovered the phenomenon of temperature coupling, in which female preferences shift in response to temperature-induced changes in male advertisement calls. Spectral parameters, on the other hand, are mainly influenced by the length and mass of vocal folds in the larynx, which scale allometrically with body size.

Our results confirm the effect of temperature and body size on male advertisement calls, but also indicate that these effects vary among species and types of notes. In species with pulsed notes, note duration and peak number are affected by temperature in a species-specific way. In contrast, in species producing modulated or tonal notes, temperature does not appear to affect note temporal structures. This may reflect a different underlying mechanism, in which modulation depends less on muscle contraction and more on the passive vibration of laryngeal structures (e.g., arytenoid cartilages) (Gerhardt & Huber, 2002). Consistent with this hypothesis, we found that in these species, SVL affects the temporal properties of notes: in species with modulated notes, SVL correlates positively only with the note duration, whereas in species with tonal notes, there is a positive (although not statistically significant) correlation with both note duration and ascending phase.

With regard to spectral properties, our results confirm a negative relationship between body size and dominant frequency, consistent with Gerhardt & Huber (2002). However, this relationship varies among species, as indicated by differences in intercepts. This suggests that, independent of the biomechanical constraints acting on vocal structures, species have evolved different dominant frequencies within these limits, possibly in response to different selective pressures.

Within the Mantellidae, acoustic variation occurs not only at the level of individual notes, but also in the temporal organisation of notes into larger acoustic units. We identified a continuum of calling patterns within Mantellidae. At one extreme, species emit either isolated notes, not organised into bouts (e.g., *Boophis boehmei*), or notes with short inter-

note intervals that do not form a true temporal structure (e.g., *Gephyromantis cornutus*). Intermediate conditions include species that group notes into bouts only occasionally and with limited regularity (e.g., *Boophis burgeri*), or species that form regular bouts that are highly variable in both duration and number of notes (e.g., *Spinomantis aglavei* and *Gephyromantis sculpturatus*). At the opposite end of this continuum, there are species that emit highly structured and stereotyped sequences of notes. In these cases, the stereotyped temporal organisation of notes defines a distinct functional unit that can itself be organised into bouts. Two representative examples are *Guibemantis tornieri*, whose calls have a highly conserved structure across all considered bout parameters, and *Spinomantis phantasticus*, whose call is composed of two short tonal notes repeated at a regular rate within bouts comprising 5-10 call units.

In accordance with Emmrich et al. (2019), the majority of the analysed calls can be classified as “multi-note non-modulated uniform calls”, as they consist of repeated identical notes with no frequency modulation across the series (e.g., *Gephyromantis boulengeri*, *Gephyromantis sculpturatus*, *Mantidactylus albofrenatus*, *Mantidactylus melanopleura*, *Spinomantis aglavei*, *Spinomantis phantasticus*). *Guibemantis tornieri* represents a notable exception, and its highly stereotyped calls could be defined as “multi-note non-modulated calls with different notes”, since they are composed of 3-4 slightly distinct note types.

The approach adopted for bout identification presents some limitations that warrant consideration. A clear example is provided by the comparison between *Guibemantis depressiceps* and *Guibemantis tornieri*. These species belong to the same genus (*Guibemantis*) and subgenus (*Guibemantis*), occur sympatrically in the rainforest of Maromizaha and exhibit broadly similar calling behaviour. In *G. depressiceps*, the call unit consists of a sequence of very short un-modulated pulses repeated at a higher rate. For this reason, we treat this unit as a single pulsed note (Figure 56A). In contrast, in *G. tornieri*, the call unit consists of a sequence of slightly longer and modulated notes, repeated at a lower rate. In this case, we considered the single note in the sequence as the basic unit (Figure 56B). Although the note of *G. tornieri* is likely homologous to a single pulse within the note of *G. depressiceps*, treating these elements as different units leads to marked differences in the resulting acoustic descriptors (e.g. duration, number of peaks, ascending phase). It is intriguing to interpret the calls of these two species as representing different stages of a potential evolutionary transition. In this scenario, a call originally composed of stereotyped sequences of discrete notes (as in *G. tornieri*) could have

undergone progressive shortening of individual notes, which eventually became pulse-like elements repeated at higher rates (as in *G. depressiceps*). This process would result in a shift in the functional unit of the signal, from a single-note call, through a multi-note call to the pulsed-note call.

Figure 56 - Comparison between the oscillogram silhouettes of two species of the subgenus *Guibemantis*. A: Oscillogram of a call of *G. depressiceps*; B: Oscillogram of a call of *G. tornieri*.

Despite the difficulties in defining acoustic units that arise in some species, vocalisations in Mantellidae overall exhibit a clear hierarchical organisation. In most species, vocalisations are organised into only two hierarchical levels, with notes grouped into a bout. In this case, the note itself corresponds to the call unit, and its temporal and spectral structure is likely to encode all information important for species recognition. These functional units (notes) are then repeated in bouts, which improve the transmission efficiency of information and may also play a role in mate competition. In some species, however, notes are first organised into stereotyped sequences, which are further arranged into higher-level bouts. In these cases, the first-level stereotyped sequence may function as the call unit, encoding information important for species recognition.

Although the functional role of different acoustic properties can ultimately be inferred only by examining female responses to variation in these traits (Gerhardt & Huber 2002), patterns of within- and among-male variation in call properties suggest that static traits mediate species recognition, whereas dynamic traits may signal male quality (Gerhardt 1994). Accordingly, the most static traits in anuran vocalisations are likely to encode species, population or even individual identity for the receiver, thereby improving species

recognition. Dynamic traits, on the other hand, may convey information important for mate-quality assessment or simply improve the communication efficacy (Gerhardt, 1991; Gerhardt, 1992).

Accordingly, call temporal parameters, such as pulse duration, pulse rate and call duration, allow the discrimination of closely related species, whereas spectral parameters tend to be more conserved. However, the same temporal parameter can encode different information: for instance, variables such as call duration can be defined as static (Bee et al., 2010), dynamic (Castellano & Giacoma, 1998; Gambale et al., 2014), or intermediate (Grenat et al., 2013) depending on the species considered.

According to Rose (2019), temporal information is coded primarily in the spatiotemporal patterns of activity of auditory-nerve fibers, but the representation of temporal information mainly occurs in the central auditory system. Two types of neurons have been identified with a fundamental role in selectivity for pulse rate: long-interval cells, responding well to slow pulse rates but failing to respond phasically to fast pulse rate, and interval-counting neurons, responding to intermediate or fast pulse rates, but only after a threshold number of pulses presented at optimal intervals.

In light of these mechanisms, a pattern emerges in the analysed species: notes with faster peak rates are also typically longer in duration (e.g., *Mantidactylus betsileanus*, *Gephyromantis malagasius*), whereas shorter notes have slower peak rates (e.g., *Gephyromantis sculpturatus*, *Spinomantis aglavei*).

The importance of temporal parameters in species recognition has been widely demonstrated. For example, in 1987 Schwartz demonstrated that females of *Hyla microcephala* can use pulse repetition rate to discriminate between conspecific and heterospecific calls. Moreover, many studies documented greater differences in pulse rate and pulse temporal parameters (e.g., inter-pulse interval) between species in syntopy than in allopatry, consistent with a pattern of reproductive character displacement (Schul and Bush, 2002; Lemmon, 2009; Grenat et al., 2016), but also between closely related anurans belonging to diploid/polyploid complexes (e.g., *Bufo viridis* complex – Castellano, 1998).

These findings highlight the importance of accurately describing temporal acoustic parameters, a level of detail that remains insufficiently explored in Mantellidae. In this context, we detected notable differences in pulse rate among three cryptic and often sympatric species of the subgenus *Chonomantis* (*Mantidactylus albofrenatus*, *Mantidactylus melanopleura* and *Mantidactylus opiparis*). Although these species emit

bouts with a similar number of notes, they differ markedly in note rate (highest in *M. albofrenatus*, lowest in *M. opiparis* and intermediate in *M. melanopleura*).

Further investigations are needed to clarify the functional relevance of these temporal properties and the role of call structure in species recognition in Mantellidae.

5 Conclusion

In conclusion, we observed a broad range of diversification patterns among the analysed species in the family Mantellidae. From a morphological perspective, substantial differences are evident in body size, limb proportions and head shape. Ecological pressures may have played a key role in shaping these frogs' traits: limb proportions in stream-edge species differ significantly from those of arboreal and forestal species, although additional relevant differences may have gone unnoticed. Head shape differs markedly between Boophinae and Mantellinae; however, the genus *Spinomantis* shows a *Boophis-like* head shape, which could represent either an adaptation to arboreal life or a conserved ancestral trait. The observed correlations between limb proportions and eye position and size should also be further investigated.

The analysed species are also characterised by highly different vocal repertoires, but some trends have been detected. The correlation between calling site height and degree of amplitude modulation is independent of phylogeny and may represent an important finding regarding vertical ecological gradients shaping acoustic properties of anurans' vocalisations, in accordance with the acoustic adaptation hypothesis. Note parameters and their organisation in higher hierarchical structures (such as bouts or more stereotyped series, which we define as calls) may represent a static trait enabling reproductive isolation. Further analyses are also required to assess the potential effect of calling site height on the dominant frequency of Mantellidae calls. Supported by our results, we propose that vertical habitat use represents a key ecological factor shaping both morphological and acoustic variation. Finally, the observed differences in the vocalisation of *G. cornutus* and *G. sculpturatus* provide a promising case study for investigating their phonatory mechanisms and may potentially reveal previously unrecognised ecological or biomechanical constraints that have led to this acoustic differentiation.

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